

JOURNEY OF NATIONAL WINNING COACHES IN THE FIELD OF CAMPUS JOURNALISM: A MULTIPLE CASE STUDY

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 21

Issue 8

Pages: 809-836

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2007

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.12677225

Manuscript Accepted: 06-05-2024

Journey of National Winning Coaches in the Field of Campus Journalism: A Multiple Case Study

Daniel D. Somosot Jr.,* Carla Mae P. Landasan, Rovejane S. Salvacion

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

This multiple case study aimed to explore, discover, and comprehend the journey encountered by national winning journalism coaches in Davao del Norte Division. In this study, five (5) participants were chosen to participate in an in-depth interview who were national winning coaches in different fields of campus journalism who could experience the phenomenon being studied. Thematic analysis was used in analyzing the data. This study revealed the unique characteristics of each case. Five (5) major themes emerged for preparations and training, four (4) themes for stories of failures, and another four for moments of triumph. On the other hand, another four themes emerged in surviving the challenges. From the thoughts of inspiration, three (3) themes appeared. The results of this study were deemed significant to the participants and designated school journalism mentors and coaches for they will get broader knowledge and essential skills that could be applied in coaching students in the field of campus journalism.

Keywords: *national winning coaches in journalism, preparations and training, failures and triumphs, overcoming the challenges in coaching journalism, thoughts of inspiration*

Introduction

Every student's success depends heavily on their coaches; without them, some students would not be able to thrive in their academic endeavors. Academic coaching requires the experience of coaches, particularly in writing competitions such as journalism contests. Competent, passionate, upbeat, goal-oriented, encouraging, patient, clear communicator, and informed are qualities that make a winning coach. For their student writers to be effective and prolific, coaches need to have these attributes. Like any other endeavor, campus journalism is also faced with challenges, especially for journalism coaches. Developing student writers and gaining support from peers and superiors might provide obstacles for coaches at times.

In Bangladesh, Ullah (2021), the lack of professional education of coaches in journalism is one of the primary reasons for the rise of ill-trained writers. The insufficiency of knowledge on professional ethics and the insufficiency of formal journalism training among journalism coaches contributed to incompetent student writers. Furthermore, in Pakistan, Martinez (2021), coaches in journalism experienced great difficulties due to insufficient background and training on the subject. These problems may cause poor performance of the journalism coaches and low academic achievement of the student writers.

Moreover, in some rural areas of Malaysia, journalism teachers face difficulties teaching students journalistic writing because of the lack of adequate resource materials. Teachers made use of outdated references in teaching their student writers. It has befallen them to buy updated references for teaching journalistic writing using their resources (Nortajuddin, 2020).

In the Philippines, according to Estella (2020), some of the teachers assigned as journalism trainers are not equipped; they lack the mastery of journalistic writing and methods. Issues are not on the teachers' instructional communication strategies but on the rigorous practice of journalism coaches. On the other hand, in the far-flung school in Cebu, 87% of journalism coaches are faced with problems of the lack of support from their Schools Division Office. Many potential coaches are not given opportunities to join seminars and workshops to enhance their journalistic writing skills. Aside from that, they also encountered problems like insufficiency of school support to encourage one to join campus journalism and deficiency of immediate financial budget for the school paper publication. Henceforth, building a campus journalism club in every school is not guaranteed to have enough student participation (Omay, 2020).

In the Division of Davao del Norte, particularly in the Talaingod District, many elementary and secondary schools regularly joined the Division Schools Press Conference. Journalism coaches selected the best and competent students in their schools to compete in the journalism event. Most of these elementary and secondary schools are situated in remote areas; hence they have limited access to training and writing workshops; and limited exposure to media or newspapers. The coaches must give the resources that pupils require in situations such as these. Journalism coaches provide training and seminars for their chosen student writers when students are unable to attend those offered at the regional and divisional levels. To support journalistic demands, they also offer essential resources including newspapers, news clips, and other references. Even though there have been times when coaches have struggled to inspire their student writers to put in the necessary work, some of them go on to win journalistic contests.

Furthermore, this research study focused on the experiences of the teachers who are coaching campus journalism. Although there are different related studies of this phenomenon conducted by Atucha (2018) and Sabaysabay (2020), the researchers have not come across any local study that focuses on the experiences of national winning journalism coaches. Hence, this prompted the researcher to conduct this study to provide new information about the ordinary yet unresolved and serious problems like the school's lack of support, financial problems, and training and exposure that most of the winning journalism coaches are experiencing today.

The national winning coaches will find particular significance in this study as their concerns will be acknowledged and taken into

consideration in order to overcome the difficulties they have faced. Furthermore, the researchers were motivated to do this study because they thought it would affect the school that produces national champion coaches. They would be able to learn more about the ramifications and difficulties of mentoring journalists. This would provide a pertinent idea that would direct the victorious journalism coaches and assist them in mentoring their student writers.

Research Questions

1. What are the unique characteristics of each case of winning journalism coaches?
2. How does each case describe the preparations and training in the field of Campus Journalism?
3. What are stories of failures and moments of triumphs experienced by each case of a winning journalism coach in the field of campus journalism?
4. How does each case of winning journalism coach survive the challenges they experienced in campus journalism?
5. What are the thoughts of inspiration that can be shared with others by each case of winning journalism coaches in the field of campus journalism?

Methodology

Research Design

Qualitative methodology is most useful when researchers strive to collect data based on human perceptions and understanding. It is a means for exploring and understanding the individuals or groups ascribed to a social or human problem, which involves questions and procedures, gathering participant data, and data analysis (Creswell, 2013). In addition, qualitative research is used to explore the causes of potential problems that may exist. It is also defined as research methods that delve into participants' observations, experiences, thoughts, and feelings, resulting in a narrative, descriptive account, or practice (Stake, 2018).

In this study, the researchers utilized the qualitative design to explore, probe, and understand the experiences, challenges, causes, and insights of the national winning journalism coaches by investigating several factors with prolonged engagement, in-depth interviews, and data-gathering procedures. Further, this design is apt to use since it aids in understanding the experiences, human situations, and problems of winning journalism coaches at the national level.

Also, multiple case is the appropriate approach since it explores real life through detailed, in-depth data collection and multiple bounded systems over time involving numerous sources of evidence and reports case themes and case descriptions (Creswell 2013). Yin (2009) added that the multiple case study approach is a research strategy entailing an empirical investigation of a contemporary phenomenon within its real-life context using multiple evidence sources. It is especially valuable when the boundaries between the phenomenon and context are blurred. The researcher can provide the literature with a significant influence from the contrasts and similarities when the case studies are compared.

The researchers employed multiple case types of research in this study since they gathered the untold viewpoints and perspectives of national winning coaches in journalism regarding their experiences, challenges, and insights using multiple sources of evidence from the chosen participants. An in-depth interview focused on five research questions used to achieve comprehensive descriptions of this research, including viewpoints and experiences the participants faced. The interview helped determine insights of national winning coaches about their experiences in coaching journalism.

Using qualitative research applying multiple case study methods helped account for the experiences and the factors of the challenges contributed by national winning coaches in journalism in the Division of Davao del Norte. It provided a refinement of understanding that encompasses critical contextual conditions, facilitating a profound appreciation of national winning journalism coaches' cases. Moreover, it emphasized their challenges, the causes of their challenges, and their coping mechanism. It further used this data to explore their shared and distinct practices to win and achieve the journalism competition.

This qualitative research using multiple case studies helped the researchers understand and explore national winning coaches' experiences in journalism through the purposive sampling technique, which identified the chosen participants that satisfy the inclusion criteria. Conducting an in-depth interview requires the researcher to follow the suggested protocol by the SMCT REC. Thematic analysis and content analysis were applied to analyze the participant's data, and trustworthiness and ethical considerations were strictly observed in this research.

Participants

This qualitative research using multiple case studies has a minimum of five (5) participants. Hence, there were five (5) national winning journalism coaches in different public schools of Davao del Norte Division in this research. The said number was sufficient to obtain the study purpose recommended by Polkinghorne, (1989) as cited by Flynn & Korcuska (2018) that 5-25 samples are enough to obtain data to describe and discuss the interest of the phenomenon.

In this research, researchers opt to apply purposive sampling. Purposive sampling is a technique used to get rich information from the chosen participants selected based on their willingness to share their experiences with the researcher (Polkinghorne, 2005). Using

purposive sampling, the pre-inclusion criteria in selecting participants are as follows; first, the participant must be secondary public school teachers in the Division of Davao del Norte. Second, he or she must be teaching English subject; third, a school paper adviser in his or her assigned institution; and must be a coach in campus journalism at different levels and have won the National School Press Conference from 2012-2020. The criteria for selecting the participants included male and female teachers I, II, and III who had different experiences and challenges as national winning coaches in journalism.

In qualitative research, the participants should be well informed about the conduct of the interview and should be aware of where and when the interview is scheduled. The main goal was the complete confidentiality of every participant (Fossheim & Ingierd, 2015). The chosen participants were given informed consent indicating the purpose, time, and date of the interview.

As the researcher in this study, they sought permission from the chosen participants to record the entire interview with the assurance that the data gathered from them especially the printed ones and e-data were stored, or a system for retention or storage and disposal of the data after the lapsed of the prescribed period for storage. The five coach participants were given pseudonyms to ensure confidentiality in the conduct of the study.

The first case, the Consistent Coach is a consistent winner in both Division and Regional School Press Conference and a 3-time winner at the National level. She is 47 years old, a Teacher II in Davao del Norte Division, handling English subjects in grade 7 and Special Program in Journalism for Grade 8 and 10 in her respective school. She was a winner in the National Schools Press Conference (NSPC); 3rd Placer Best in Infomercial NSPC 2016 held at Clark, Olongapo City, 2nd Placer News Presenter NSPC 2019 held at Pangasinan, 4th Place Technical Application Radio Broadcasting, and Champion Best in Technical Application TV Broadcasting during the NSPC 2020 held in Tuguegarao City.

The second case, the Devoted Coach, is 27 years old, a Teacher I in the Division of Davao del Norte and currently handling Grade 11 Oral Communication subject in her institution. She has served DepEd Davao del Norte for three years now and had been coaching journalism for two years. This coach is into journalism when she was still a student. She was an Associate Editor when she was in second-year College and Editor-in-Chief way back in her third and fourth-year in college. During her first year in coaching journalism, she failed at the national level, which is why she strived hard and did her best as a coach. Because of her determination, she won 6th Place and 1st Place in Radio Broadcasting during the National Schools Press Conference 2020 held in Tuguegarao City.

The third case is the Newbie Coach. He is a first-timer journalism coach and won in the National Schools Press Conference 2019-2020 as 2nd Placer in News Writing held in Tuguegarao City. He is 27 years old, a Teacher I in the Division of Davao del Norte, and is handling English 10 for two years now. He has been a Student Journalism coach for one year now.

The fourth case is the Versatile Coach; she is versatile because she has handled different journalism events from 2011 to 2020. Her events were feature writing, sports writing, news writing, editorial writing, sci-tech writing, and radio broadcasting. Every year, she wins in the Division and Regional Schools Press Conference and become a national qualifier in different events. In her nine years of coaching journalism, she became a campus journalism official in Davao del Norte Division. Last year, she won at the National level as the 3rd Placer in Radio Broadcasting held in Pangasinan. After winning the national level, she became more motivated and determined in coaching and looking forward to being a champion in the next NSPC competition.

The fifth case is the Passionate coach; he is passionate because even though he is no longer the journalism coach in his assigned school, he continues his passion by helping and mentoring the new journalism coach. During his time, he always brought honor to his assigned school by winning journalism contests in both Division and Regional level every year. Passionate coach is 56 years old handling English 7 to 10 and has served DepEd for 25 years. According to his co-teachers and former students, he is a rigorous coach to his students, yet a very kind mentor. He was coaching journalism from 2011 to 2015. He won the Division and Regional Schools Press Conference many times in copy reading, news writing, and feature-writing. Last 2013, he won as 3rd Placer in Copy Reading in the National Schools Press Conference held in Ormoc City.

	<i>Consistent Coach</i>	<i>Devoted Coach</i>	<i>Newbie Coach</i>	<i>Versatile Coach</i>	<i>Passionate Coach</i>
Age	47	27	27	50	56
Position	Teacher II	Teacher I	Teacher I	Teacher III	Teacher III
Years in Service	13 years in service	3 years in service	2 years in service	28 years in service	25 years in service
Years in Coaching	6 years in coaching	2 years in coaching	1 year in coaching	9 years in coaching	5 years in coaching

Instruments

Qualitative investigators used different ways of gathering data procedures such as documents, observations, and interviews (Creswell, 2007). Participants’ experiences and observations are the basis of this research and will be acquired through in-depth interviews. Austin (2015), the most common type of data collection is the in-depth interview where the interviewer collects data directly from the interviewee. This technique is perfect when gathering highly personalized data and comprehending and understanding participants’ hidden feelings, motivations, attitudes, and beliefs on a particular subject.

In this research, participants were answer based on their chosen language during the in-depth virtual interview as long as they are comfortable with it. they gave follow-up questions not seen on my interview guide to get more profound and clear ideas and thoughts from the participants. An in-depth interview is of great help for providing the participants the chance to share their experiences and perceptions related to the topic.

Morgan et al. (2016), observation protocols are useful for collecting first-hand information, and it was also be conducted to create a relatively incontestable description. In the context of our study, the setting for these primary data sources was the different schools in Davao del Norte Division where they are currently employed. The researchers conducted the study from January 2021 to March 2021 for the academic year 2020-2021. they interviewed all public secondary teachers in the said division who are coaching journalism in the English category and are national winning coaches in Journalism from 2010 to 2020. This also allowed them to gather information to develop vicarious experiences for the reader's benefit. Moreover, observation of the chosen participants was done on several occasions.

In connection with this, the researchers used secondary sources to support the outcome of this research. Streefkerk (2018) said that secondary sources provide second-hand information and commentary from other researchers. It describes, interprets, or synthesizes primary sources. In this research, the researchers used secondary sources found in journals, reading from the internet, and books to support the investigator's information to the chosen participants. With the help of the secondary sources, gathered data from the chosen participants were strengthened.

Furthermore, this study was conducted on both national winning coaches in journalism and their direct fellow journalism advisers. This study also employed triangulation specifically triangulation of source since it used different data sources (the five cases themselves and their direct fellow journalism advisers). It has also been viewed as strategy in qualitative research to test the validity through the meeting of data from different sources.

Procedure

As a researcher, they took rigorous steps in the collection of data procedure. they also engaged in a series of events to collect data before arriving after the study. Creswell (2007) supported those qualitative researchers tied up in series of events in the collecting data. A vital step was to find participants involved in this research, the convenience and accessibility of material, and the place to conduct the study to obtain accurate information.

This study undergone a research ethics review in the SMCTI-REC to guarantee the ethicality of this research. Ethics will check thoroughly every detail of the study. They provided corrections and comments to have a compelling research study, and the data gathering shall commence only after the release of the ethics clearance. After the ethics reviewed the entire protocol and approved the study, they secured a letter of permission from the Dean of the Graduate School of St. Mary's College, Inc. before the conduct of my study.

After which, they sent permission to the respective Schools Division Superintendent of Davao del Norte Division to ask for approval to conduct the research study. After the approval, they sought permission from the schools' administrator where the chosen participants are assigned. Each participant from the different schools was provided with a letter of consent to inform them about the purpose of the study and asked them to affix their signature before the interview.

Letters of permission were sent through electronic, scanned, or other alternative means adhering to the Inter-Agency Task Force (IATF) health and general guidelines and protocols. This is in response to the government's command concerning the emerging infectious diseases, and the spreading of the COVID-19 pandemic, and to guarantee the safety and security of the selected participants.

As the investigators of this research, they conducted first a virtual orientation of the selected participants through Google Meet that were used in this study. For the chosen participants who could not join the orientation, they informed them about the study through a phone call. If the chosen participants will not join the orientation, it is the researcher's responsibility to find a replacement for another participant in my study. In finding a replacement for my chosen participants, they considered the inclusion criteria that this study needed.

Furthermore, schedules were set based on the availability and convenience of the participants; however, this was done in one participant at a time. The data collected in this research was included the in-depth interview of the national winning journalism coaches. The researchers provided an interview protocol that serves as their guide during the in-depth interviews. They gathered data through audio recording and transcribed the result of the interview. It is a process of scrutinizing data through listening, watching, and converting audio materials into a manuscript (Moore & Llompart, 2017). They asked the permission of the participants to record all their responses in the interview and it was recorded verbatim using an audio recorder while taking notes to get key points shared by the participants. Significantly, the researchers asked follow-up relevant questions related to the chosen topic until the saturation point was reached for the data enrichment. Transcription of the information gathered from the informants followed.

In addition, transcribing was a laborious process requiring ample patience and perseverance to collect data. It is vital in the data analysis, which would become a basis for the research's major themes. The gathered data from the transcription was checked, analyzed, and scrutinized by the analyst and research adviser.

Data Analysis

Data analysis was the limelight of this multiple case study. The researchers documented and transcribed the data gathered and employed procedures to evaluate the data prudently. This multiple case study utilized coding, thematic analysis, and the formulation of significant themes and cross-case analysis to analyze the data collected.

In analyzing the data, once all the research interviews were transcribed and checked. Coding was applied. According to Sutton (2015), coding refers to the topics' identification, issues, similarities, and differences revealed by the participants' narratives. Through this, improvement of the themes will emerge.

In this study, this was done in a thorough marking, highlighting, and naming of the relevant and potential ideas from the participants' responses. After this, they collated all the data into groups identified by code. These codes allowed the researchers to improve insight into the shared meanings and main points of the data that recur. After an exhaustive information translation process, researchers have gone through another recording cycle and recognized text-connected sections by a typical subject that permits me to file the text into classifications and in this way close and lay out a system of topical thoughts connected to it.

Meanwhile, the thematic analysis involved describing and identifying explicit and implicit ideas within the data, that is the theme. Codes were normally evolved to address the identified themes, and raw data was applied as summary markers for later analysis (Hsieh and Shannon, 2005 as cited by Assaroudi et al., 2018). Furthermore, thematic analysis can be used to analyze qualitative information and systematically gain knowledge and empathy about the person, a group, an organization, an interaction, and a situation or phenomenon (Guest et al., 2016). In this study, the investigators guaranteed this through a systematized way of interpreting and analyzing the collected data by carefully identifying potential themes or ideas like other data utilized to develop more fixed and succinct results conclusions.

Additionally, the formulation of major themes is another way of uniting the varied data inductively from the participants' responses before theoretical comprehension of the study. The potential themes are based on the phenomena or characteristics being studied: from already agreed-on professional definitions found in the literature review: from researchers' values: personal experience, and theoretical orientations, and local, common-sense constructs (Vasileiou et al., 2018). In the context of this study, they carefully reread and analyzed the suitable phrase to get potential themes that were necessary to the phenomenon under study. Also, they assured that biases did not exist and the intentions of the researchers; hence fair means of formulating the theme undergone.

Ethical Considerations

The Belmont Report (1974) attempted to summarize the basic principles identified by the Commission during its deliberation. The three basic principles recognized in our traditional practice will apply to the research ethics concerning human subjects: the principles of respect for person, beneficence, and justice (Podany, 2017).

This study was focused to explore, discover, and understand the challenges experienced by the national winning journalism coaches, the causes of these challenges, and in what way the participants address such challenges. For the participants, who would be considered vulnerable in this research, it is of utmost importance for the investigator to guarantee their safety and full protection, considering their experiences, environment, and sensitivity to the topic. Thus, Belmont Report (1974) highlighted the core principles that form the universally accepted basis for research ethics. These are respect for persons, beneficence, and justice.

The first principle, respect for a person, pertains to the investigator's courtesy towards the participants and their rights to autonomously decide in taking part in this research. According to Creswell (2007), participants must be autonomously treated being a person who makes decisions or deliberates for herself about general goals and then acts upon them and how to protect them from harm. To observe this principle and to identify that the selected research participants are all adults.

In the context of this study, the data collection procedures were appropriate as we raised to the SMCTI -REC and our panel of examiners with regards to the steps that we have done before the conduct of their study. Importantly, they sent letters of permission to the Schools Division Superintendent of Davao del Norte Division and to the respective school principals to ask for approval before the conduct of this research.

Also, they sent an informed consent to the national winning journalism coaches asking and signifying their permission to participate in the study actively and willingly. As such, they made sure to respect my participants, asking them if they genuinely desire to be part of this research as informants. Furthermore, when researchers reached the agreement, they encouraged them to read and sign the digital informed consent signifying their willingness to participate in this study. From there, they prepared and set our interview schedule at a time that is convenient for both.

As part of their consent prior to the actual interview, researchers oriented the participants about their rights of the study. They were entitled to the protection of their identity in this undertaking; they used coding in the in-depth interview to ensure confidentiality of their responses and their personal identity through anonymity. They were also given the right to ask questions before, during, and after the interview and full right to withdraw and refuse from the study whenever they feel that they do not want to participate anymore in the interview; Likewise, researchers asked their permission beforehand to allow them to record the whole duration of the interview for

them to gather all their responses. When investigators gained their permissions, they eventually started the interview. Questions in the interview were only revolved around the phenomenon of national winning coaches in journalism and they contacted them to check transcripts of their interview. Moreover, they are also allowed to add, delete, or change some of the printed responses if they see some responses that are erroneously printed.

The second is beneficence, refers to making efforts in securing the well-being of the research participants and minimizing the harm. Benefits to research might develop to friendship among researcher and other participants, knowledge will be acquired from participation or the opportunity to do well for the society or receive the esteem of others (Creswell, 2007).

In this research, researchers would guarantee that the findings of this research would be useful, beneficial, and advantageous to my research participants. The results of his study would not just be useful to their chosen participants but also to other journalism coaches for them to do their best in coaching their student writers and to the DepEd officials who are concern about this program. They made sure that the research's purpose maximized the benefits and minimize the possible risks of my informants throughout the conduct of this research study.

The study helped them reduce the burden that participants possibly feel by sharing their personal insights and problems of the topic. Researchers would let them speak for themselves and to address issues and concerns about their failures and moments of triumphs as a winning coach in journalism. This study would develop participants' perseverance and encouragement in pursuing their rule as journalism coaches despite the challenges in coaching their student journalist.

In their reports, researchers made sure not to include any information that would identify the participants, for it is their duty as investigators to uphold their confidentiality and of the identity of the respective institutions, taking responsibility to their safety and well-being by providing, a pseudonym to each participant. Furthermore, the researchers considered the schedule of the conduct of the study depending on the convenient time of the informants after the approval of the permission to conduct the research study; they would also consider the rescheduling of the date and time of the interviews as the chosen informants requested.

Lastly, the ethical principle of justice requires reasonable allocation of the risk and benefits as a finding of the investigators. All classification of the people their gender, ethnicity, race, etc. must be similarly subjected to the benefits and risk of the study, and individuals must be excluded and included only for motives that need to do with the questions of research (Scott, 2018). Contributions of the participants must be acknowledged for doing their part to the best of their ability for the success of the research. (Bloom and Crabtree, 2006). To ensure justice, researchers also sent copies of research in every institution where the informants are teaching.

To apply the ethical principle of justice in this study, justifiable and fair in terms of recruitment in choosing informants must be considered by the investigators and the location for the conduct of the study. Further, as researchers, they would cater to their needs first before the research's aims. The questions that were asked by the researchers to the participants must be relevant and significant under study. They guaranteed that the informants were accommodated properly, and due credits must be given for all their efforts and the time they contributed.

Furthermore, the investigators provided token of appreciation and refund for internet expenses to the participants since the interviews were done through virtual. Those were given to them for their voluntary participation and willingness during the interview as they lend their time, effort, and courage in sharing their experiences to make this study possible.

Add to the adherence of Belmont's report; this study conforms to Republic Act No. 10173, otherwise known as the Data Privacy Act (DPA), which aims to reconcile the privacy of right with the efficient utilization of information. Under the policy statement of the Act, it is understood that even as the law guarantees the protection of an individual's fundamental right to privacy. The free flow of information for growth, national development, and innovation must also be ensured by the investigator. The DPA, while upholding the data subject- a person's rights whose personal information is collected, stored, and processed- do not impede access to information, which may hinder progress and advancement. It does not impede the processing of personal data for research. The act supports the information's freedom, initiatives for data sharing, and the responsible use and processing of personal data.

In this study, researchers guaranteed that the anonymity and informants' privacy maintained wherever possible to increase the security of data processing. they ensured to use code names so as not to reveal the identity of the chosen informants. Also, the collected data handled properly, utilizing, and placing it on a secured cabinet wherein it would be inaccessible, visible only to an authorized person. Further, only the researchers, adviser, and panel of experts would have access to the gathered data from the chosen informants.

In summary, in the research's conduct, the researcher made sure to apply and treat equally all the concrete measures mentioned above to come up with meaningful experiences with the chosen informants. This served as their guide and basis to take different actions and thought in the aspects of this research.

Results and Discussion

Profile of National Winning Coaches in Campus Journalism

Table 1 presented the profile of each case as described by the national winning coaches in the field of journalism who served as the

participants of this study. As shown in the table, The Consistent Coach is a Teacher II and teaching for 13 years in the Division of Davao del Norte and has been coaching journalism for six (6) years. She is a consistent winner in both Division and Regional Schools Press Conference and has won many times in National Schools Press Conference.

The Devoted Coach is 27 years old, a Teacher I, and teaching for three years in the Division of Davao del Norte. She is motivated to win and used her failures in journalism to strive hard until she won the National Schools Press Conference in her second attempt. The Newbie coach is a first-timer coach in journalism. He is 27 years old and teaching as Teacher I in the Division of Davao del Norte. The Versatile coach is 50 years old and currently teaching as Teacher III in the Division of Davao del Norte and has served DepEd for 28 years. She has also been coaching campus journalism for nine years. The Passionate coach is a 56 years old and a Teacher III in the Division of Davao del Norte. She has served DepEd for 23 years and has been coaching journalism for five years.

Table 1. Profile of Each Case

	<i>Consistent Coach</i>	<i>Devoted Coach</i>	<i>Newbie Coach</i>	<i>Versatile Coach</i>	<i>Passionate Coach</i>
Age	47	27	27	50	56
Position	Teacher II	Teacher I	Teacher I	Teacher III	Teacher III
Years in Service	13 years in service	3 years in service	2 years in service	28 years in service	25 years in service
Years in Coaching	6 years in coaching	2 years in coaching	1 year in coaching	9 years in coaching	5 years in coaching

Accounts on the Individual Characteristics

Presented in Table 2 of this study are the accounts of the unique individual characteristics of each case. As a researcher, it was vital for me to know the unique characteristics of each case. It included the individual personalities and attitudes.

First is Consistent Coach; she always described herself as supportive to her student journalists that they need her most. According to her fellow adviser, she is also a counselor because she always advises her students to help them grow. Consistent Coach is also a role model for she exhibited the right attitude that student journalists must be acted. Lastly, she won the Radio and TV Broadcasting competition at National Schools Press Conference.

Second is Devoted Coach. She described herself as a passionate and hardworking coach because she continues her task as a journalism coach despite the tasks as a classroom teacher. She is also a time-oriented person because she considers time an important thing, especially in coaching her students. Another, her fellow adviser, described her as goal-driven, always aiming to win the competition and bring honor to her school. Finally, she is a Radio Broadcasting Coach champion in the National Schools Press Conference held in Tuguegarao City.

The third is Newbie Coach. He described himself as an enthusiast in learning new things and eagerly adopting new trends. Also, his fellow journalism coach described him as the type of coach who always gives encouragement and advice to his journalists; that is why his writers are motivated to win the competition. Finally, even if he is a first-timer coach, he became a winner in the news writing competition during the NSPC 2019.

Fourth is the Versatile Coach. She described herself as a determined coach because she is persevering and time bound. Her fellow journalism coach added that she has a strong personality in facing failures concerning campus journalism. She is also dedicated to her task as a classroom teacher and a journalism coach. She won the National Schools Press Conference in Radio Broadcasting.

Finally, the fifth is Passionate Coach. He described himself as a dedicated person for his unwavering devotion to his assignment and task given by his school administrator. According to his fellow teacher, he is also a success-driven because he aims to win the NSPC competition; that is why he doubled his effort and strives hard to win the competition. Passionate Coach considers himself an imitator coach because he imitates the performing mentors and learns based on their experiences. Lastly, he won the National Schools Press Conference in copy reading, wherein he got third place.

Table 2. Major Themes and Core Ideas on the Unique Characteristics of Winning Journalism Coaches

<i>Cases</i>	<i>Essential Themes</i>	<i>Supporting Statements</i>
Consistent Coach	The Supporter	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The particular qualities that make me proud are being supportive to my writers, being supportive in terms of finances, giving them advice, being supportive at all times in their lives when they needed a coach.
	The Counselor	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Every student wants somebody to listen to them; they want friends. If they go to the right person, most especially to their coach, to ask for advice, they will appreciate that much, and their coach has impacted their lives and has built a close relationship with them. She is also the type of coach who is willing to listen and always there for her journalists when they have problems, and she treats them as part of her family.
	The Model	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> For me modeling to them what you wanted them to be made me unique. As a coach, you must be a model to them; you have to act and show them the things and skills they needed to learn in journalism.

	The Radio and TV Broadcasting Coach Winner	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Last 2014, we won National Schools Press Conference in Olongapo City in Radio Broadcasting that was third place in Radio Broadcasting Best in Infomercial then last 2018, we won as Best News Presenter and recently the NSPC 2019 held in Tuguegarao City my team in TV Broadcasting was the champion although it is a collaboration in Region XI but the Sto. Tomas National High School was the best in Technical Application in TV Broadcasting and 4th Place in Technical Application in Radio Broadcasting.
Devoted Coach	The Passionate and Hardworking	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> I am a passionate and hardworking coach. If you are not passionate enough and hardworking enough, you will not survive as a coach because aside from being a classroom teacher, you need to extend more time to train your writers or train students to become writers.
	The Time-Oriented	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The particular quality that I have is I am very time-oriented. As a coach, you have to be time-oriented; you have to persevere because there are many things to consider during the preparations. I establish deadlines in every submission of my writers' output because time is very precious for me. I am punctual during our practice since I love journalism so much. I do not want to be late for a meeting or practice.
	Goal-Driven	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> From the start that she became my fellow adviser in this field; she always set goals in winning journalism and hoping to bring honor and pride to our school so that our principal and fellow teachers become proud of us.
Newbie Coach	The Radio Broadcasting Coach Champion	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> I am handling copy reading and headline writing aside from that radio broadcasting and online publishing. Those three categories won in DSPC and RSPC. During the NSPC, my radio broadcasting won in the first place.
	The Enthusiast	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> I am a type of coach who exhibits broad curiosity. I want my writer to eagerly adapt to new technology platforms and eagerly learn the trends. I have the enthusiasm to learn new things. And as a coach, I am making my writer enthusiastic about learning and discovering new ideas useful in news writing.
	The Encourager	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> From what I have observed on him as his fellow mentor, he always encourages his writer to be more motivated in the competition and do his best no matter what happens. And he lifts the confidence of his writer by giving advice during the competition.
Versatile Coach	The News Writing Coach Winner	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> It was my first time coaching journalism, and I was so proud that we got second place in news writing in English secondary Sir held in Tuguegarao City.
	The Determined	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> I have the perseverance to do things and be time-bounded; I see to it that the time that I needed is exact because the time for me is significant. She does not easily give up, so it does not discourage her when she has failures, specifically in this field. It pushes her to do more. She made sure that she gave her full support to her writers to be motivated in every competition.
	The Dedicated	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> I am also diligent in doing things, specifically when it pertains to working as a journalism coach. I am dedicated to doing this task.
Passionate Coach	The Radio Broadcasting Coach Winner	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> We won Best Anchor in Radio Broadcasting and Third place in Technical Radio Broadcasting for NSPC 2019.
	The Dedicated Coach	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> I am dedicated to my work and assignment. I am devoted to doing the things that my principal assigned to me, especially in this endeavor. I made sure that I always do my best so that the results will be good and make my principal happy.
	The Success Driven	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> We have been together for many years in coaching, and I have witnessed his dedication. Every time we joined competitions, he always has a goal to bring home awards. That is why he strives hard, most especially in preparing our student journalists.
	The Imitator	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> I do not consider myself a unique coach; it is just I trained hard; I asked for advice from those veterans and winning journalism coaches. I imitated and copied their styles in coaching and on how they train their student writers. I consider their pieces of advice in training my writers.
	The Copy Reading Coach Winner	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> I handled different events like editorial cartooning and copy reading; during the NSPC Sir, I won third place in copy reading.

Cross Case Analysis on the Preparations and Trainings of Winning Journalism Coaches

Table 3 of this study presents the accounts on the preparations and training of each case in the field of campus journalism. Bringing together the responses of the participants in all cases, the researcher has come up with the following themes which are common to

some, if not all 5 cases: 1) equipping oneself with the latest trends, 2) having a history in writing, 3) being molded by experts, 4) doing intensive training, and 5) intensifying screening of writers.

Equipping Oneself with the Latest Trends

Staying informed on trends is important to help journalism coaches build credibility and value and to show that they know where their field is heading in the future. Successful journalism coaches spend time keeping up with the latest news and developments in their field. In this study, this is evident to the statement of Consistent Coach when she shared that she did many readings and shared the information with her journalists, especially the latest trends in our country. Moreover, Passionate Coach also shared that he updates himself with the current events in the country by reading magazines, newspapers and watching the news on television. He believes that topics during journalism press conference competitions are about the latest trends in the country, so he made sure that he shared that information with his journalists.

Having History in Writing

Most of the performing coaches were being developed by their experiences in their chosen field. Hence, having experience in journalism is an edge in coaching student journalists. It helped them make coaching more manageable and more meaningful since they already have a background in this field. In this study, this is evident in the three cases. Consistent Coach shared that she was a feature writer way back in her secondary years and became an Editor-in-Chief in their school publication when she was still in college.

Meanwhile, Devoted Coach also reiterated that she was a student writer for many years and competed in schools press conferences during her secondary days. When she was in college, she became a member of their college publication. Moreover, Newbie Coach mentioned that his journalism background shaped him during his high school days. He also mentioned that he was a sportswriter and Editor-in-Chief in their school publication and won many times in Division and Regional Schools Press Conference.

Being Molded by Experts

An expert person brings a big impact to every individual and aids them to be a performing individual in their field of specialization. Thus, an expert is someone with which can develop a long-term relationship that is centered on building the mentee's growth and development and can offer support, wisdom, and teaching over time. In this study, this is evident to the preparations of Consistent Coach when she shared that her coach when she was in high school molded her to become a good writer and inspired her because of the attitude being shown by her mentor.

In addition, Devoted Coach also shared that there was one teacher who shaped her in campus journalism, and that was her former coach. She added that with the help of her coach, she learned to love journalism and inspired her to explore more in this field. Furthermore, Newbie Coach shared that his high school journalism coaches molded him. He added that they taught him the things that he needs in this endeavor. Also, he mentioned that the journalism speakers he attended were very competitive and intelligent in this field. Because of them, Newbie Coach learned a lot and applied those learnings in coaching his student.

Moreover, Versatile Coach shared that her school principals shaped her by teaching her to become dedicated and passionate in handling campus journalism in their school. She added that her school administrators taught her to be positive always despite the challenges she encountered. Lastly, Passionate Coach shared that he learned a lot in this field by focusing on the journalism speakers' discussion. Another, he mentioned that he was also taught by his friends who are also performing coaches in campus journalism.

Doing Intensive Training

Training gives everyone a great understanding of their responsibilities and the knowledge and skills they need to do certain tasks. This will enhance their confidence which can also improve their overall performance. In this sense, five cases shared their experiences about doing intensive training. Consistent Coach shared that aside from attending Division and Regional trainings in journalism, they also have school-based training for their student journalists. They excused their journalists in their respective classes for two weeks before the proper competition. She added that they do not allow their journalists to attend their classes because they wanted them to focus and prepare themselves for the upcoming competition.

Thus, Devoted Coach mentioned that they had a rigorous practice before joining the competition. They attended Division and Regional training for qualifiers and conducted school-based training with the collaboration of all journalism coaches in their school. Also, Newbie Coach shared that they attended Division Schools Press Conference, Division Summer Camp, Special Training in Journalism for School Paper Advisers, and Regional Enhancement Training in Campus Journalism for national qualifiers.

Meanwhile, Versatile Coach shared that they attended the Division training and rigid regional training for the national qualifier. She mentioned that they had undergone several training in order for them to upgrade their coaching skills. Lastly, Passionate Coach shared that he used to prepare his journalists at the school level. He excused his journalists in their class for them to give focus on their practice. He added that assigned from school-level practice; they also attended division and rigorous regional training.

Intensifying Screening of Writers

Pursuing the finest campus journalist can make a massive difference in the endeavor to win in a competition. This practice helps

journalism advisers to track down potential student-writers who have enough knowledge and background in journalism. In this study, this is evident to the experience of Versatile Coach when she shared that she selected those journalists who have a high interest in writing and prepared the holistic aspect of their journalists.

In addition, Passionate Coach shared that at the start of the school year, they started to scout potential writers by conducting an elimination round. They also pinpoint the students who will be included in the elimination round. Aside from teaching them journalistic skills, they also enhance the attitude of their journalists.

In this part, unique themes responded by each case were; being knowledgeable on journalism contest and standard and benchmarking from previous winning entries were the responses of Consistent Coach; having an open mindset for learning was the response of Devoted Coach; and adopting a self-disciplined approach through self-improvement and being consistent were the responses of Versatile Coach.

Table 3. *Cross Case Analysis on the Preparations and Trainings of Winning Journalism Coaches*

Themes	Cases				
	1	2	3	4	5
Equipping Oneself with the Latest Trends	√				√
Having History in Writing	√		√		
Being Molded by Experts	√	√	√	√	√
Doing Intensive Training	√	√	√	√	√
Being Knowledgeable on Journalism Contest and Standard	√				
Benchmarking from Previous Winning Entries	√				
Having an Open Mindset for Learning		√			
Adopting Self-discipline Approach through Self Improvement				√	
Being Consistent				√	
Intensifying Screening of Writers				√	√

Cross Case Analysis on the Stories of Failures and Moments of Triumphs in the Field of Campus Journalism

Table 4 presents the cross-case analysis on the stories of failures and moments of triumphs of winning coaches in the field of campus journalism. Considering all the responses in all cases, the researcher has come up with the following themes which are common to the participants: disappointment in writers' attitude, monetary challenges, being pressured due to unsupportive colleagues, facing disappointment of writers' performance, fulfillment in students' learning, fulfillment in students' achievement; grateful of the opportunities, and giving pride and honor to the institution.

Disappointment on Writers' Attitude

A student journalist who intentionally creates a disturbance in practice that directly interferes with the coaches' ability to instruct other student journalists' ability to learn is considered disruptive. Disruptive behavior can have adverse effects not only on the training environment but also on the whole journalism class. Meanwhile, Consistent Coach shared that one of her failures in coaching journalism is the disappointment of writers' attitudes. Her young journalists were good at writing; however, they lack a sense of responsibility as writers, and these inappropriate attitudes affect their performance.

Furthermore, Devoted Coach mentioned that she was also dealing with the writers' inappropriate attitude. She said that her journalists were all intelligent; however, some of them are hard-headed and boastful. In order for them to have a good performance, she talked to them to address their issues. In addition, Newbie Coach stated that he experienced difficulties in dealing with students who have inappropriate attitudes. One of his journalists was overconfident and used to ignore the given task during their school-based practice. As a result, during the contest, they failed to win the competition.

Monetary Challenges

Having a financial challenge is one of the failures of coaches in terms of school activities and competition. This made the school become pressure to find ways to address this issue. In this sense, Consistent Coach shared that she experienced many challenges, and one of those is the financial problem. Her school brings a considerable number of participants to represent different categories in journalism. However, this becomes a challenge since they shouldered the fare, food, registration fee, and allowance of the participants. Likewise, Devoted Coach said that they are from a big school and have many writers to represent their institution in journalism competitions. However, their PTA is not enough to help them, so that their school must find ways to pay the registration fee of the participants, food, and fare.

Furthermore, Versatile Coach shared that the NSPC 2020 was a very challenging year for her because the schedule of the competition was moved, and they have already booked a plane on the first schedule. This situation challenged her since they need to rebook a plane, and they must pay tickets for their journalists worth a substantial amount. Lastly, Passionate Coach shared that they came from a small school, and they do not have enough budget to pay their obligations in joining the competition.

Being Pressured due to Unsupportive Colleagues

Helping hands with teachers is one way to have a better school performance and productive students. However, having unsupportive colleagues might affect everything, especially the journalism competition. In this sense, Devoted Coach shared that the allocated time for their practice is not enough since some of her fellow teachers did not allow their students to skip their class and attend their school training. This made her become pressure, so she needs to schedule their practice every weekend.

Furthermore, Versatile Coach stated that she failed to get support from co-teachers. This frustrated her since some of her colleagues did not give participants enough time to attend their school-based practice.

Facing Disappointment of Writers' Performance

The primary purpose of every journalism coach is to help their student journalists enhance their journalistic writing skills and help potential students widen their knowledge about writing. For this to be possible, coaches did their best and exerted effort to provide for the needs of their journalists. However, despite their efforts, some student journalists failed to perform their tasks well and failed during the journalism contests.

In this sense, Devoted Coach shared that she felt disappointed when her journalists did not qualify for the regional level during the division competition despite the efforts and time she had invested in them. Furthermore, Newbie Coach shared that he gave all his time, efforts, and sacrifices for his journalist to win, but his student did not do his best and failed the competition. Also, Passionate Coach mentioned his disappointment during the NSPC competition, particularly to his editorial cartoonist. He trained his journalists well, and during the training, his student came up with sound output; however, during the competition, his journalist's output was not as good as it has been during the training.

Fulfillment in Students' Learning

Having students with passion and love in their chosen field motivates teachers. In the journalism field, it is a success for every coach to see their journalists use their learnings in this field by writing articles without any command from the coaches and posting articles on social media with or without the coaches' knowledge. In this sense, Consistent Coach shared that she considered herself as a successful one when she saw her writers initiated writing their articles by observing every school activity.

Also, Devoted Coach mentioned that she was very proud to see their journalists applying their learnings in this field by posting their outputs on social media. Lastly, Versatile Coach mentioned that her former winning journalist was using her learnings before in journalism by applying it during her college because that student was a member of the college writers' guild.

Fulfillment in Students' Achievement

One of the achievements of every teacher when they saw their students became successful in their chosen field. In this sense, Consistent Coach said that her former journalists are now excelling in their studies in college. Some of her journalists enrolled in the Mass Communication program and became honor students. Also, Devoted Coach mentioned that since they do not have face-to-face competitions, her journalists joined an online writing competition to pursue their passion in writing, joined an online writing competition.

Similarly, Newbie Coach shared that his former journalist who won NSPC became a qualifier in an online writing competition. It made him so proud to see his journalist performing well as an online content writer. Meanwhile, Versatile Coach shared that she has a former journalist who is now her fellow coach in journalism. She said that it is her achievement because her previous performing writer is now part of the Division of Davao del Norte journalism mentor. Lastly, Passionate Coach uttered that his former writers are now excelling in their respective fields. Some of them are teachers, and some are journalists.

Grateful for the Opportunities

Being given trust and responsibility is a privilege for every coach; this helps them become more motivated. In this sense, Consistent Coach shared that she was happy winning in the NSPC because she was given an opportunity to serve her district as resource speaker and facilitator in District-Wide Schools Press Conference.

In the same manner, Versatile Coach uttered that when she won the journalism competition as a coach, the School Paper Advisers elected her as part of division officials in campus journalism. This made her proud of herself and her success since the officials are all successful coaches. Also, she added that many schools in her district invited her to be a speaker in their school-based training.

Giving Pride and Honor to the Institution

Coaches bring pride and honor when they win competitions; this would make them more motivated to join in other competitions. In this sense, Newbie Coach shared that it was his first time joining a competition, and fortunately, he became a national winner. His school administrator and fellow teachers were happy, for he brought pride and honor to his school. Furthermore, Passionate Coach said that he gave a legacy to their school as he won the NSPC. Also, he added that he brought pride not just to his school but also to their division.

In this part, unique themes responded by each case understories of failures and moments of triumphs were; disappointments over unfair results was the response of Consistent Coach; having difficulty due to unaligned field and gaining recognition due to one's success were the responses of Newbie Coach, and development of the character of writers and realization to one's capacity to compete with performing coach were the responses of Passionate Coach.

Table 4. *Cross Case Analysis on the Stories of Failures and Moment of Triumphs in the Field of Campus Journalism*

Themes	Cases				
	1	2	3	4	5
Disappointment on Writers' Attitude	√	√	√		
Monetary Challenges	√	√		√	√
Disappointment over Unfair Results	√				
Being Pressured due to Unsupportive Colleagues		√		√	
Facing Disappointment of Writers' Performance		√	√		√
Having Difficulty due to Unaligned Field			√		
Fulfillment in Students' Learning	√	√		√	
Fulfillment in Students' Achievement	√	√	√	√	√
Grateful for the Opportunities	√			√	
Gaining recognition due to One's Success			√		
Giving Pride and Honor to the Institution			√		√
Development of Writers Character					√
Realization of One's Capacity to Compete with Performing Coach					√

Cross Case Analysis on Surviving the Challenges in Campus Journalism

Table 5 presents the cross-case analysis on surviving the challenges in winning campus journalism. Considering all the participants' responses in all cases, the researcher has come up with the following themes, which are common to the two, if not all five cases: seeking assistance from others, learning from failures, having open communication, and being optimistic.

Seeking Assistance from Others

It was said that "Two heads are better than one." In solving a dilemma in the field of campus journalism, a coach alone cannot solve it. However, working together hand in hand, seeking assistance from others who can help with such problems as the school head, fellow teachers, and parents would significantly change the campus journalism environment. Meanwhile, Consistent Coach shared that she asked her fellow journalism coaches to help her in coaching writers. She also mentioned that she experienced financial problems and a lack of gadgets to be used by her writers. However, she easily addressed those challenges with the help of her school administrator and fellow teachers.

In addition, a fellow adviser of Case 3 mentioned that to address the challenges of Newbie Coach in coaching an area not suited to his field, he asked the advice and help from his former mentor at the same time his fellow journalism coach. Also, Versatile Coach shared that in financial constraints, she asked for the helped of their school administrator and PTA since she cannot handle it on her own. Lastly, Passionate Coach said that to address financial constraints; he asked for support from others by soliciting money from the neighboring company, fellow teachers, and politicians.

Learning from Failures

The road to success is paved with failure, and the most successful people have usually failed multiple times in their climb to the top. It could be argued that achieving a high level of success is virtually impossible without some form of failure. In this sense, Consistent Coach shared that there is no better teacher in life than failures. Because she believes that failures bring the opportunity to learn things better, it helps us learn from our mistakes, and it makes us rethink and reconsider finding new ways and strategies to achieve our goals. Furthermore, Devoted Coach shared that failures helped her to become a better coach today and used it as her stepping stone in reaching her dreams.

Meanwhile, Newbie Coach also shared that he diverted those challenges into meaningful experiences by using his failures as the instrument in winning the journalism contest. Versatile Coach also mentioned that she used those negative experiences as her instrument to face challenges she encountered in coaching her journalists. Lastly, Passionate Coach shared that he learned a lot from his failures, and those failures test him to be a performing coach in this field.

Having Open Communication

Effective communication between coaches and student journalists is essential to build a trusting and strong coaching relationship. Young people, as student journalists, are still learning how to communicate successfully, and they often rely on their coaches to take the lead and teach them how to communicate in this unique relationship. This is evident in this study when Consistent Coach shared that as a coach, he did not listen to one student only; instead, she talked to all members if there is a misunderstanding among them. She

also added that talking wholeheartedly to her student journalists helped establish a good relationship with them.

In the same manner, Devoted Coach shared that she talked to her student journalists about the possible results after the competition. She made sure that her journalists embrace the outcome and consider it as an avenue to learn more. She also added that she always explained to them the do's and don'ts and the consequences of their action. Lastly, Versatile Coach shared that she called the attention of her journalists and talked to them wholeheartedly, giving them choices to continue or stop joining the competition. She also explained to them the importance of having a good attitude and discipline in this field.

Being Optimistic

In dealing with an alarming situation in journalism, being optimistic is one of the attitudes that coaches must teach to the student writers, hoping for the best outcome. In this way, the coaches' attitude towards coaching journalism can show a positive result. This is evident when Devoted Coach shared that she always looks at the brighter side of every situation. She explained to her journalists that every effort and sacrifice they have made will always be for their good. Furthermore, Newbie Coach shared that looking at a particular challenge positively motivates him to do things despite not being an expert in a particular field. He added that since he is an optimistic person, he believes that he can do it and believed in winning the competition.

In this part are the individual responses of each case under surviving the challenges; employing diligent efforts for improvement, knowing the judges, and being mindful to the new trends in writing were the responses under Devoted Coach; doing own research was the response of Newbie Coach; having time management and setting action plan were the responses under Versatile Coach, and being considerate to student writers and praying to God were the responses of Passionate Coach.

Table 5. Cross Case Analysis on the Surviving the Challenges in Campus Journalism

Themes	Cases				
	1	2	3	4	5
Seeking Assistance from Others	√		√	√	√
Learning from failure	√	√	√	√	√
Having Open Communication	√	√		√	
Employing Diligent Efforts for Improvement		√			
Being Optimistic		√	√		
Knowing the Judges		√			
Being Mindful to the New Trends in Writing		√			
Doing Own Research			√		
Having Time Management				√	
Setting Action Plan				√	
Being Considerate to Student Writers					√
Praying to God					√

Cross Case Analysis on the Thought of Inspiration by Each Case in Winning Campus Journalism

Table 6 presents the cross-case analysis on the accounts on the thoughts of inspiration of each case in winning campus journalism. Consolidating all the responses of the participants in all cases, the researcher has come up with the following themes, which were common to some, if not all five cases: be committed to your craft; learn from others; and be open-minded.

Be Committed to your Craft

Being committed to your craft is extremely powerful because it influences how you think, how you sound, and how you act, which then feeds the perception engine of what others think of you. Making a real commitment means that you try harder, look for innovative solutions when faced with obstacles, never consider quitting as an option, and be persistent and highly resilient.

This is evident in the response of Consistent Coach when she shared that she has to continue what coaches have started and love journalism to overcome the challenges that would come in coaching. She also added that when coaches failed on endeavors, they must be strong to face it; their time will come and achieve their dreams. With the same thought, Newbie Coach also shared that coaches must have perseverance and commitment to continue their passion as journalism coaches until winning at the national level.

Meanwhile, Versatile Coach shared that coaches must never give up despite their challenges in this endeavor. The most important in this field is the learnings that student journalists may get along their journey as journalists. She also added that coaches must have perseverance in coaching their journalists; they must sweat it out, love more and fuel their interest more. Lastly, Passionate Coach also reiterated that coaches must be committed to their task as coaches.

Learn from Others

People with a perpetual learning mindset treat mistakes and challenges as part of the learning process. They do not see mistakes as failures; instead, they give them new information they can use as they continue to find ways to solve a problem or challenge by learning from their own experiences and others. This is evident to Consistent Coach when she shared that learning from others may help someone

be an excellent and effective coach in this field. They became successful because their experiences shaped them out. On the other hand, Devoted Coach uttered that coaches must consider campus journalism as an avenue to be a better person by learning from fellow coaches and so with the judges. Lastly, Newbie Coach also reiterated that acquire learnings from your fellow coaches and apply those learnings in coaching writers.

Be Open-Minded

Effective coaches can recognize and use their students' strengths while at the same time finding ways to improve their weaknesses. An essential part of coaching effectiveness and expertise is a coach's ability to be introspective and reflective with an "open mind" that allows him or her to critically look back at past experiences, recognize weaknesses, and revise techniques when necessary. This is evident in the response of Devoted Coach when she shared that coaches in journalism must be open-minded in recognizing the learnings learned from training. These trainings will help them strengthen their skills to be a more effective coach.

Furthermore, Versatile Coach shared that coaches must be active in attending training and workshops because these are the important factors to widen their knowledge and enhance their skills in coaching. Lastly, Passionate Coach reiterated that coaches must not be discouraged for their failures; rather, they must be open-minded and attend training that the Department of Education conducted.

In this part are the themes under thoughts of inspirations responded by each case; be true to yourself was the response of Consistent Coach; be a goal-oriented was under from the responses of Devoted Coach; believe in yourself was from Newbie Coach; perceive setback as an avenue for self-enhancement was the response of Versatile Coach; maintain good relation with administrator was the response of Passionate Coach.

Table 6. *Cross Case Analysis on the Thoughts of Inspiration by Each Case in the Field of Campus Journalism*

Themes	Cases				
	1	2	3	4	5
Be Committed to your Craft	√		√	√	√
Learn from Others	√	√	√		
Be True to Yourself	√				
Be Open-Minded		√		√	√
Be Goal-Oriented		√			
Believe in Yourself			√		
Perceive Setback as Avenue for Self Enhancement				√	
Maintain Good Relationship with the Administrator					√

Conclusions

Unique Characteristics of Winning Coaches in Journalism

From the data gathered through the interviews to the five cases, researchers discovered their unique characteristics.

Consistent Coach described herself as a supportive coach to her writers, especially in situations when they need her most. Her fellow adviser in journalism mentioned that she used to give advice and guidance to the journalists for them to grow. She is also a role model to her journalists by showing the appropriate attitude that journalists must possess. Moreover, she won in the Radio and TV Broadcasting at the National Schools Press Conference competition.

Devoted Coach described herself as a passionate and hard-working coach in journalism because, despite her duties as a classroom teacher, she still performs well and gives enough time to coach her journalists. Furthermore, she described herself as a time-oriented person; she is keen on beating deadlines and respects the time of others. Moreover, her fellow adviser described her as a goal driven coach because she aims to win in every competition. She did her best in coaching journalists in the different categories she handled during the DSPC and RSPC. She won as champion in the NSPC.

Newbie Coach described himself as a first timer in coaching journalism. According to him, he is very enthusiastic about adopting new ideas and strategies in this field. His fellow adviser mentioned that he is a type of coach who regularly gives encouragement and advice to his writer. Though coaching is new to him, he still proved to others that he could be a good coach. His writer landed in second place in the News Writing competition during the NSPC 2019.

Versatile Coach described herself as a determined person in coaching journalism because she has perseverance and has a solid affinity for being time bounded. Her fellow journalism coach declared that she has a strong personality so that whatever failures come in her journey as a coach in this field, she fights until she wins. She is a dedicated coach and a classroom teacher. In her years of coaching, she won the Radio Broadcasting competition.

Passionate Coach described himself as a dedicated coach for he has a dedication in his assignment and task given by his school administrator. His fellow teacher mentioned that he is also a success-driven individual determined to achieve something or be successful. All of his behavior is directed toward the aim of winning. Aside from that, Passionate Coach is also an imitator coach for

she imitated and copied the style of other performing coaches. Lastly, he is a Copy Reading coach winner, and he got the third place during the NSPC competition.

The Preparations and Training of Winning Coaches in Journalism

This part presents the differences in the preparations and training of winning campus journalism coaches. The five cases shared their thoughts from their responses, five (5) themes emerged in the cross-case analysis: (1) equipping oneself with the latest trends; (2) having history in writing; (3) being molded by experts; (4) doing intensive trainings; and (5) intensifying screening of writers.

Equipping Oneself with the Latest Trends

Staying informed on trends is important to help individual builds credibility and value and to show where your field is heading in the future. Successful people spend time every day keeping up with the latest news and developments in their field. Participants' response have admitted that they must read different materials and watch news for them to be updated on the latest trends in our country. With this, they become updated and knowledgeable on the trends and share those information to their students.

It is evident to the study of Bird (2018) stated that staying updated with the latest news and happenings around the world is very important for all. Knowing the latest news and updates and new events which are occurring every now and then in our country, or some other countries or may be within your state is necessary. Individual must always listen to or read the current news on TV, radios, or newspapers, as much as possible. This will give an idea of the happenings and events around, especially about economic news, political news, business and finance related news, general current events, and other global news.

Furthermore, Bouchillon (2021) stated that it is important to keep up with current trends in journalism since it determines what is currently accepted to be the best way to students. However, just like some fashion trends can be ridiculous passing fads, some trends in journalism may also change rapidly. It is important for teachers and coaches to stay current in their knowledge but decide for themselves which research trends best fit their coaching style.

For instance, Schleicher (2015) uttered that equipping with the latest trends requires innovation and a change in the approaches towards teaching and learning. Teachers are key actors in creating this context for learning and growth and can help establish effective learning environments. As we move into the future, new forms of educational provision will be needed that recognize the essential role that teachers play in transforming classrooms and to support them in their endeavor.

Having History in Writing

Coaches with background knowledge and experiences in journalism are most likely successful as they train every journalism student. Their experiences will be their edge as they train and mold their student to be a good writer. Reflected from the results, participants admitted that they have history in writing during their high school and college days.

In connection to this, Mason (2017) said that a well-shaped coaches in journalism know the importance of skills and training and knowing the specific skills that each writer needs to work on. Having background in this field make coaches feel comfortable and ease since they knew already the things that they need to do in terms of coaching and in competition as well. With the help of their experiences, they must be one's to bring out the best writers and most of the time, successful coaches are those who have enough background in the field.

Furthermore, Lent (2018), stated that background knowledge and experience is an essential component in learning because it helps us make sense of new ideas and explore more experiences. Prior experience in journalism really does help journalists when they must undergo situations during the process. They show that having prior experiences is an edge of every individual to perform well in every given task.

Moreover, Hailikari, et al. (2018), prior knowledge has long been considered the most important factor influencing coaching and learning process. The amount and quality of prior knowledge of each coach positively influence their task as they coach every student journalist in their learning process and in developing their skills in journalism. Inadequate prior knowledge is an important issue to consider because this will lead to ineffective coaches and hampered the learning of student journalists in learning the skills in this field.

Being Molded by Experts

One of the most important things in achieving goals is learning to ask for help when needed. Knowing when and how to ask for help can make navigating this unknown terrain much easier and save each time by avoiding mistakes. It is helpful for the participants to acquire knowledge and acumen from experts in journalistic writing and coaching. It helps to know the necessary strategies to become an effective coach. Reflected from the results, all cases mentioned that they became successful in this field because of the helped by their coaches, mentors, and administrators.

In line with this, Curtis (2014) stated that acquiring insights from experts is not limited to technical questions rather it is also giving guidance and imparting knowledge to a certain individual for the improvement. Thus, acquiring acumen from others should, therefore, be seen as a positive step; one that enhances health and wellbeing and happiness.

In addition, Brown (2017) said that acquiring insights and expertise from others allows us to surround ourselves with people who can make us feel good and facilitate further development. These people create optimism and hope that we can deal with challenging situations, which improves our resilience. If we can ask for help and obtain feedback, we can overcome setbacks and grow which is the key traits needed to enhance our resilience.

For instance, Robins (2018), posited that it is one thing to acquire knowledge; quite a different thing to acquire wisdom. For knowledge acquisition effort to be both successful and effective, one must learn as much from the experts. Such experts provide perspective from the trenches, having been “over the mountain” — they know what works and what does not, and perhaps what might work better than something else. You may not be able to directly acquire their wisdom, but you’ll likely gain valuable insight from it, and some of that wisdom just might rub off onto you.

Doing Intensive Trainings

It is said that practice makes perfect. Doing intensive trainings for students to memorize or adopt concepts can be defined as that of the use of an idea to gain familiarity and expertise which is important to achieve the desired goals particularly in the field of journalism. Reflected from the results, all cases stated for them to prepare their journalists in national level, they must undergo rigid trainings and practice. With this preparation, journalists will gain confidence and skills that are useful in the competition.

This is congruence to the study of Maksl (2014) posited that students benefit from practice because they can apply knowledge through interaction. Students connect with the material when they work with texts and concepts beyond a one-time exposure. When students practice using the knowledge through application, they connect with information on a deeper level. For instance, when learning about writing, students must write. They must hone the voice, tone, and style of their writing. This cannot happen unless they revise, see examples, and learn to improve their own work. Students cannot transfer a lecture on good essay writing into an actual good essay without practical application.

On the other hand, Mohammed (2016) said that conducting drills to students are associated with a regimented style of instruction, they do have a place. Drills are used successfully when teaching students technique. Thus, teachers need to make sure that when having students practice, there is a clear link between concept and action. Students must be able to relate what they are doing to what they are learning. Similarly, drills are not effective when students are not prepared enough, they will not be able to maintain a pace if they are still unclear about a concept. Furthermore, drills are typically for more basic knowledge or for a more physical understanding. If teaching about more abstract concepts, a drill methodology would not be appropriate.

Thus, Llama (2017), doing meticulous teaching and training will give students a great understanding of their responsibilities and the knowledge and skills they need to do in a certain field of endeavor. This will enhance their confidence which can also improve their overall performance. Furthermore, it will enhance not just their cognitive aspect but also their behavior in responding a certain situation.

Intensifying Screening of Writers

Intensifying screening of writers can make a huge difference in the endeavor to win in the competition. This practice helps journalism advisers to track down potential student-writers who have enough knowledge and background in journalism. Based on the findings of the study, the two cases uttered that preparing journalists holistically will help them become competent in every competition. Thus, this will be done through selecting the potential writers who has high interest in this field.

According to Hunt (2016) posited that selecting best student-writer enables the teacher discover students with potential in journalistic writing with a love of writing and communication to make their output worthwhile. On the other hand, one of the main purposes of tracking best writers is to provide a few options for teachers and have them self-differentiate. Understanding why this is so important requires teachers to examine a fundamental idea about students’ motivation.

As supported by Gracey et al. (2016), screening programs for student writers in entering campus journalism are widespread, and their use is increasing. Screening of writers is used to identify those who may be eligible and capable to be part of the program and represent their school in the journalism competition.

In addition, Misasi (2016) stated that there are a couple of important ideas to understand about the pursuing finding best writers in order to truly appreciate its connection them. It is important to pursue best writers that this strategy is seemingly very important to teachers to be able to personalize learning within the context of academic standards. However, it requires that teachers shift their instructional strategies, and choice may be one of the best vehicles for getting there, for it allows teachers to share in the responsibility of teaching and learning. Teachers can create viable options that students will find compelling and appropriately challenging, and then students take responsibility for choosing options that will best help them learn.

Stories of Failures and Moment of Triumph of Winning Journalism Coaches in the Field of Campus Journalism

In this part, stories of failures and moment of triumph in winning journalism coaches in the field of campus journalism are discussed. Coming from the interview, the information gathered which produced the following themes: (1) disappointment on writers’ attitude; (2) monetary challenges; (3) being pressured due to unsupportive colleagues; (4) facing disappointment of writers’ performance; (5) fulfillment in students’ learning; (6) fulfillment in students’ achievement; (7) grateful of the opportunities; and (8) giving pride and honor

to the institution.

Disappointment on Writer's Attitude

Disappointment in oneself drops the character into the lowest of lows, creating an obstacle he must overcome within himself as it holds him back and keeps him from reaching his goals. Thus, in journalism, the attitude of writers matters for it serves as their fuel to develop themselves. However, in this study, coaches sometimes feel disappointment due to their writer's attitude. This is evident when the participants shared that they felt disappointed since some of their journalists lack responsibility, are hard-headed, and boastful. These inappropriate attitudes of their journalists affect their performance.

In line with this, Puglisi (2016) posited that disappointment is one of the most powerful emotions in fiction and something all characters must feel at some point in their journey. There are different levels of disappointment and many causes for it. Characters can be disappointed in others or their circumstances and attitude, but the deepest and most meaningful moments happen when this emotion is directed toward themselves.

Moreover, Brock (2018) stated that the feeling of disappointment towards the attitude of a person is a tricky emotion to deal with because every day can bring about new situations to be disappointed over. Sometimes disappointments are truly huge and life changing. Then there are those that are small, annoying, or simply just make you cringe. Meanwhile, difficult times around the world add to our daily stressors and can heighten your reaction to negative news.

On the other hand, Haas (2016) stated that the way we handle disappointment is related to our developmental history from our relationship with our parents and other early, formative experiences. Some people seek to avoid disappointment by turning into underachievers. They unconsciously set the bar low and avoid taking risks, to prevent themselves or others from being disappointed. Without realizing it, they have decided that the best strategy is not to have high expectations about anything. Such behavior turns into a form of self-preservation. However, it also leads to a mediocre and unfulfilled life.

Monetary Challenges

Facing with problems particularly in monetary matter truly can negatively impact the mental and physical health of a person. It is also indicated stress and pressure levels for people who had money problems along with severe stress and even some depressive symptoms can lead to their performance. This is evident in this study when the participants shared that they experienced monetary challenge because their school shouldered the registration fee, allowances, and fare of their journalists.

In this line, Smith (2018) stated that like any source of overwhelming stress, financial problems can take a huge toll on your mental and physical health, your relationships, and your overall quality of life. Feeling beaten down by money worries can adversely impact your sleep, self-esteem, and energy levels. It can leave you feeling angry, ashamed, or fearful, fuel tension and arguments with those closest to you, exacerbate pain and mood swings, and even increase your risk of depression and anxiety. You may resort to unhealthy coping mechanisms, such as drinking, abusing drugs, or gambling to try to escape your worries. In the worst circumstances, financial stress can even prompt suicidal thoughts or actions.

Furthermore, Lawrence (2016) posited that while we all know deep down there are many more important things in life than money, when you're struggling financially fear and stress can take over your world. It can damage your self-esteem, make you feel flawed, and fill you with a sense of despair. When financial stress becomes overwhelming, your mind, body, and social life can pay a heavy price.

Moreover, Robinson (2016) stated that financial problems tend to impact the whole well-being and enlisting your loved ones' support can be crucial in turning things around. Even if you take pride in being self-sufficient, keep yourself and other people up to date on your financial situation and how they can help you. To prevent the same financial problems recurring, it's imperative you address both the underlying issue and the money troubles it's created in your life.

Being Pressured due to Unsupportive Colleagues

Indeed, support coming from colleagues is often associated with high job satisfaction, job involvement and a deeper commitment to one's organization. This increase in positive work attitudes can be achieved when co-workers provide task-based assistance, information, or emotional support. However, when one is unsupported by his or her colleagues, it may result to low performance and satisfaction. In this study, this is very evident when the participants mentioned that some of their colleagues did not mind to give time for their students to get out with their class to attend the trainings conducted by coaches. This made coaches felt difficult because they only have limited time to practice.

In this line, Harrison (2017) posited that co-workers can often be an important source of information for employees seeking advice, instruction or help when they are unsure of what to do. Colleagues can often provide information to support or discourage certain activities. This can be particularly useful for reducing uncertainty about one's expected role within the organization. Additionally, co-worker support can reduce both role conflict, directly conflicting tasks and role overload or excessive demands given the amount of resources.

In addition, Chiaburu (2016) stated that colleagues can also influence employee opinions and attitudes. Co-worker support is often

associated with high job satisfaction, job involvement and a deeper commitment to one's organization. This increase in positive work attitudes can be achieved when co-workers provide task-based assistance, information, or emotional support. Ultimately, colleagues' support can increase individual performance by providing critical information about the organization and task processes.

Furthermore, Tews (2017) mentioned that colleagues' relationships can have profound positive and negative effects on employee and organizational outcomes. Organizations should focus their attention on understanding how to foster these relationships. This can be accomplished through various means such as decreasing competition amongst co-workers, allowing supervisors to establish a friendly and helpful workplace climate and creating a strong set of standards that encourage co-worker's support. The importance of employee interactions is often overlooked. However, with the increasing focus on team-based work and flatter organizational structures, the relationships between employees become increasingly important.

Facing Disappointment of Writer's Performance

To experience the real excitement of success, one must experience bitterness of failure for once, and from our errors we can learn more than learning from our success, and this does not mean that human deliberately fail to succeed, no one accepts that. However, in this study, the participants shared that it is very difficult to win in the competition because of the performance of their writers. They also shared their disappointments that some of their journalists didn't give their full efforts during the competition even if though coaches already give everything; efforts and time.

In this line, Patterson (2017) stated that we should look at failed experiences positively after going through them, to draw the required experiences for success then to invest failure in order to succeed and changing it from a painful memory to a situation providing us with the benefits and experiences throughout our lives. Human beings are eager to success and achievement in their scientific and practical lives at all levels, but lasting success cannot be achieved constantly because human rely on trying in their lives, and the consequences of this attempt is failing sometimes.

In addition, Nolan (2017) posited that disappointment and failure to one's performance does not mean giving up as long as it would not be the last objective in a person's life, but it becomes a motivation for success and a ladder to climb and moving towards the best to achieve the goals and objectives. In fact, failure is always associated with frustration and fear because of its relation to punishment from others which takes a form of disrespect, rebuke and punishment either physical or moral like, beatings and neglecting. Though, the fear of failure, committing mistakes, permanent feeling of guilt and not trying to succeed are the failure itself.

On the other hand, Renk (2016) stated that disappointment of one's performance is one of the most challenging problems that faces students as well as coaches. This problem has many causes, and it has educational, social, cultural, and psychological dimensions. However, the students' low performance on the exam or other extra-curricular activities can be defined as low or weakness of the student's mark under the normal average in a study subject level as a result of a variety of reasons including those related to the student himself, or those related to family, social and academic environment. Consequently, this may lead to frequent repetition of failure, despite their abilities that qualify them to get the best marks.

Fulfillment in Students' Learning

It is said that utilizing one's own advantage can deliver significant benefits. It is one of the critical skills for achieving success in any endeavour. It can help you solve problems, develop outcomes, and achieve desired targets. In this study, this is evident that in journalism competition, it is very important to instill to the student-writers the value of utilizing their own advantage. One participant shared that it was their success as coach seeing their journalists exercising their skills in writing through writing articles and posted in social media.

In this line, James (2018) posited that teaching students in utilizing own advantage enables problem solving and provides creative insight that allows them to look at things from a different perspective, regardless of whether they are developing a new product, refreshing strategy or finding an original way to stay ahead of the competition. Thus, typically, it can be an enhancement to their existing performance, an expansion to their output or a complete change of direction.

Meanwhile, Caan (2016) stated that learning to utilize own advantage and doing something new and untested or unproven may seem risky. However, the biggest risk of all for a modern business may in fact be not utilizing this advantage or innovating. Reluctance or inability to improve your performance may leave your output unable to compete, diversify or simply operate. Output and performances that fail to utilize own advantage may run the risk of falling productivity and efficiency.

Moreover, Maddock (2016) stated that utilizing own advantage can be precarious but the potential benefits can be vital to the continuing success of any performance and competition. Starting a small business is a matter of self-selection and self-determination. While utilizing own advantage can allow them to step into an alternate reality, part of a social order in which each person regardless of gender, race, ethnicity, religion, birth or circumstances can achieve their fullest potential and receive recognition for their achievements.

Fulfillment in Students' Achievement

Seeing our students successful in their career is strongly linked to the positive outcomes we value. It is somehow a sense of reward for our hardwork and passion we imparted and instilled to them. This is evident to this study when participants shared that they become triumphant in thier career when they see their former students successful in their own field that some of them are joining competitors

in an online writing competitions due to limited face-to-face interactions.

In this line, Broward (2017) posited that the success of the students our institutions serve is not only a goal but rather a responsibility. Connecting students to the correct resources and support when needed is critical. This often comes in the form of proactive advising. While students are slow to ask for assistance, they readily receive it when offered. The common goal of our institutional partners is to ensure they are able to intervene early and often, creating pathways to success in and outside of the classroom. And when we see them successful, it is then a great reward for us.

In addition, MacKenzie (2018) stated that making students successful made a lasting impact when students experience and appreciate the connection between what is studied and how it relates to the real world. When students thanking us for information they are now using in their jobs we feel satisfied and fulfilled. Sometimes, we see it as our rewarding endeavor for we can say we did our job well.

Moreover, Smith (2016) mentioned that nothing is more rewarding to me as a teacher than seeing my students succeed. It could be as simple as a note or an expression on a student's face. Or it could be as significant as seeing a student turn a class assignment into a presentation or of knowing the teaching methods they modeled are used in other classrooms. But faculty members say that, whatever the method, it means a lot when they see their student succeed.

Grateful of the Opportunities

There are just a few elemental forces that hold our world together. The one that's the glue of society is called trust and responsibility. In this study, participants shared that because of their success as coaches, they were fortunate and honored that they were given the trust and responsibility.

In this line, Jaffe (2017) posited that if one is responsible and when trust is present, things go well. But when trust and being responsible is lost, the relationship is at risk. If the level of trust and responsibility is low in a relationship or organization, people limit their involvement and what they are willing to do or share. In contrast, when the trust level is high, people reward it by giving more. But, more often than not, people feel that their distrust is not safe to share. So a leader or loved one may be slow to discover that they have lost a person's trust.

Moreover, Martic (2017) stated that the hiddenness and personal nature of responsibility and trust can be a problem for relationships, teams or organizations. On how a person can fix something that is not expressed or shared and on how do he even know that trust and responsibility are lost. Paradoxically, there must be at least a little trust and responsibility in order to discuss its lack and make attempts to rebuild it, while if the loss of trust remains unaddressed, the relationship will grow more and more distant.

Furthermore, Holms (2016) posited that trust and responsibility are often related to leadership and power, but it is not a given. To be effective, a one must earn the trust and portray his or her responsibility of his or her constituents to ensure their participation and allegiance. Indeed, any successful relationship whether it's leader to follower, consultant or coach to client or the relationship between spouses, siblings and friends relies on a level of trust and responsibility that must be earned.

Giving Pride and Honor to the Institution

Giving pride and honor to a particular institution has emerged as an important emotion to encourage learners to be part and develop the existing success of it. In this study, this is evident when participants shared their success stories in winning journalism competition. They shared that through winning the competition they were able to give pride and honor their respective schools.

In this line, Kernaghan (2016) posited that the emotion pride and honor can increase motivation and perseverance. Giving pride and honor to a workplace is the feeling of deep pleasure or satisfaction which comes from your achievements. Taking pride in your work is a massively important role for any professional. The fact that teachers and coaches make the world work, should be a source of immense pride and satisfaction.

Furthermore, Dyson (2017) stated that giving pride in the work and workplace is essential to fostering a more energized workplace. And when employees feel such energy they are more likely to want to come to work and do a good job. Morale improves, too, and few workplaces can do without a strong team spirit. It can also give satisfaction to the work and achievement they get. It is an accomplishment that tends to show others your worth as employee.

In addition, Mazer (2018) stated that giving pride and honor to a certain workplace is never easy. Giving pride and honor is not happy talk. It is pride centered on purpose. Employees who love what they do and the organization to which they belong demonstrate their support for their organization in words, but most especially, in actions. They do whatever is necessary to get the job done and done right. That is the kind of pride every employer should strive to engender and give so much satisfaction to their workplace.

Surviving the Challenges in the Field of Campus Journalism

In this part, the coping mechanism of each case in the field of campus journalism are discussed. Coming from the interview, the information gathered which produced the following themes: (1) seeking assistance from others; (2) learning from failures; (3) having open communication; and (4) being optimistic.

Seeking Assistance from Others

Collaboration skills enables journalism coaches to successfully work toward a common goal with fellow coaches, teachers and principals. It includes communicating clearly, listening actively to others, taking responsibility for mistakes, and respecting the diversity of colleagues. Based on the results from data gathered, as for coaches to survive the difficulties, they reach out from their fellow journalism coaches, administrators, and other people who could help them address certain problem.

Besides, Ribeiro (2020) stated that collaboration improves the way of team works together and problem solves. This leads to more innovation, efficient processes, increased success, and improved communication. A team reaches a common goal through a combination of individual and team-driven efforts. With a clear goal in mind, you understand your role and the purpose of your work. This means you can combine your abilities and knowledge to improve your workflow and achieve your common goal. Aligning on these goals leads to team-wide support, contributing to all-around skill-sharing and increased productivity.

In addition, Page (2019) asserted that asking for help from other coaches allows to surround ourselves with people who can make us feel good and facilitate further development. These people create optimism and hope that we are able to deal with challenging situations, which improves our resilience. If we are able to ask for help and obtain feedback, we can overcome setbacks and grow. Furthermore, research found that that high performing coaches are more likely to seek advice from their colleagues, former mentors, and higher ups. This may be because high performers want to improve, and as such seek advice to identify and improve their weaknesses.

Moreover, Kashyap (2020), having collaboration in the field of work is a sign of effective team as it harnesses the best out of two or more individuals together. Once there will be a collaboration, there will always see positive results as the biggest fears of checking whether the teams are able to perform together will be eliminated. This will generates a circle of knowledge and lets each team members to understand their role.

Learning from Failures

One of the most challenging duties faced by a coach is that of keeping the team upbeat, positive, motivated, and optimistic after losing in a competition. Coaching is a lot easier when the team is winning however, it would be the other way around when the team is losing. It would be difficult if the team is dejected, frustrated, and with little confidence for the future. It is in these moments that the overall success of a coach is often measured.

Based on the findings of the study, the participants mentioned that they must learn from the failures they experienced in this field.

As supported by Curtis (2016) said that every journalism enthusiast has suffered and experienced through a tough loss at some point in his/her chosen endeavor -- the only difference is in how well they deal with it. Of course, some losses are easier to bounce back from than others, but the potential to be swept up in the moment is always possible.

Furthermore, Steven (2021) said that one of the things that separate the best coaches in the journalism field from their peers is their ability not to dwell on their thoughts. A tough loss has all the power to mess with your head and make you question your abilities. It's best not to over-analyze these thoughts as they can cause significant harm. Another way to get over a tough loss is to embrace them. In a sense, become happy to lose. Losing in the journalism field offers coaches and journalist much greater opportunity to grow and improve themselves to become better.

Moreover, Sicinski (2021), those who bounce back from defeat are resilient and resourceful individuals who are willing to learn from their mistakes and failures. However, in order to learn, you must have a desire to want to know what went wrong in the first place. This is where curiosity is of tremendous value. Those who bounce back from defeat are extremely curious about what exactly happened, and how they can potentially move things along in a better way. Curiosity essentially drives them forward to think of new ideas and solutions that help them prepare and plan the next steps along their journey.

Having Open Communication

Aside from teaching and coaching student journalists the skills needed in journalism, it is also the duty of coaches to teach journalists the appropriate characters and values needed in this field. Reflected from the result of this study, most of the cases said that talking heartedly with the journalists is one of their ways in addressing misunderstanding between journalists and developing their characters.

According to Laguador (2013) cited that developing positive attitude of the writers would provide them greater opportunity as they step-up to higher level of studies to broaden the scope of their responsibility and maturity to be more confident and independent. Furthermore, writers must learn to compete not with others but to compete with themselves. They have to defeat their own fears, worries and anxieties. Moreover, they need to win the battle between their own doubt and faith. Learning to accept defeat through joining in any form of competition is one good quality of recognizing certain weak points on their capability to stand out.

Besides, Sarkhedi (2020) added that being a successful writer starts with having a positive character towards learning. A positive character lets writers relax, remember, focus, and absorb information as they learn. They are ready to welcome new experiences and recognize many kinds of learning opportunities. And when they can see opportunities, hope increases.

Being Optimistic

Having a positive mindset in every situation is scientifically proven to boost happiness and motivate to achieve goals. A person who actively works to recognize the positive aspects of your life naturally start to see silver linings in challenging situations. The results showed that coaches must be positive always despite the failures they encountered during the process because those failures will help them as they continue their task as coach.

According to Gavin (2020) said that optimistic coaches especially in the competition generate well-being for themselves and for those around them. They can look on the bright side instead of getting stuck in negativity and in their failures. Optimistic people choose this way of looking at the world and they use it to frame their lives. Though there are some personality traits that favor optimism, being optimistic has more to do with reflection and practice.

As added by Peterson (2020) stated that optimism has also been shown to correlate positively with measures of mental toughness among coaches. Like findings in other domains, coaches high in optimism report greater use of approach-oriented coping strategies and less use of avoidance-oriented coping strategies when facing difficulties. They have also been shown to exhibit greater persistence following unsuccessful performances and to experience higher levels of positive affect following successful performances.

Moreover, Seligman (2018) stressed that positive person is happier because they imagine affirmative events more vividly and expect them to occur sooner. This all boosts the luscious feeling of anticipation, which is greater the more pleasurable the anticipated event, the more vividly we can imagine it, the more probable we think it is to happen, and the sooner it will be happening. Of course, it makes sense that having a sense of hope and positive attitude about the future would make us more content in the present.

Thoughts of Inspirations of Each Case in the Field of Campus Journalism

Through this study, I was able to discover the thoughts of inspirations of each case in the field of campus journalism. The following themes emerged acquired from the interview results: (1) be committed to your craft; (2) learn from others; and (3) be open-minded.

Be Committed to your Craft

There are several reasons why being committed to your craft is important. One of the most important reason is it allows coaching in journalism field to meet its goals and stick to its vision. Based on the results, most of the cases uttered that coaches must continue to what they have started and have perseverance in coaching journalists until such time they will reach their goal.

According to McIntyre (2016) that having commitment to every field is extremely powerful because it influence someone on how they think, how they sound, and how they act which then feeds the perception engine of what others think of them. Making a real commitment means that you try harder, you look for innovative solutions when faced with obstacles, you don't consider quitting as an option, and you are persistent and extremely resilient. In addition, a meaningful commitment gives someone a possible script for how to handle things when times get tough.

Likewise, Srivastava (2018) pointed out that being committed requires someone that they are ready to tread the long path to success and let go of the temptation of taking an easy route or a shortcut. Taking the long path to success invariably involves hard work. However, one must remember that the harder one works, the more benefits he reaps. One must keep in mind that with passion, commitment and hard work, any goal can be achieved.

In addition, Roomer (2019) stated that having commitment to own craft is one of the key ingredients for goal-success. If someone is not fully committed to a goal, they won't give it all the effort required to succeed. When they are not fully committed a goal — and most people aren't — they give up too quickly, work with less determination, are more likely to procrastinate, and make more unproductive decisions. Therefore, a lack of commitment is one of the most common reasons why people fail to achieve their goals.

Learn from Others

It is said that learning is a continuous process, this means that even participants have already achieved their goals and won the National Schools Press Conference; they are still learning out from their experiences or from the experiences of others. Learning from others is a very efficient way to learn things. It enables someone to get to know others better, and therefore to better understand how to behave around them. Reflected from the results, participants in this study said that learning from winning coaches' experience might help individual to be excellent and get an idea they prepare such competition.

In this sense, Montefiore (2021) stated that learning from others is associated with greater satisfaction and optimism, and improved ability to get the most from life. Working and living with others give people an edge in a volatile environment. He added that continuous learning is increasingly important to the success most especially in the field of journalism because of ever changing journalism.

Furthermore, Hassan (2021) added that learning from others is more useful than learning on our own; we evaluate ourselves more accurately when consider other opinions and listen to their experiences and learn from them. While some people completely deny the existence of others since they think that individuality is more important than relying on others, however they won't evaluate themselves and they will never realize their mistakes.

For instance, Aleccia (2018) uttered that learning from others is not a passive process, but one that requires work and commitment on our part. When we're open to learning from others, we benefit from their experience as well as our own and we can inherit their wisdom and knowledge. Others give new information wherein they can use as they continue to find ways to solve a problem or challenge.

Be Open-Minded

Open-mindedness is a positive character quality and it enables those who use it to think critically and rationally. It is so important to be able to step out of your comfort zone and consider other ideas and perspectives, especially in this day and age. For the participants in this study, they expressed that they must be open minded in learning through attending trainings conducted by DepEd for the enhancement of their skills in writing and coaching.

According to Morgan (2020), learnings opportunities from training and workshops allows journalism coaches to strengthen their communication skills wherein they became a better listener; gaining expert knowledge that give intensive exposure to a topic through presentations and discussions led by multiple experts; and networking with others that give opportunities to meet other people who share your interests; and renewing motivation and confidence to pursue your goals and find your enthusiasm rekindled. This can lead to higher productivity and fulfilment of professional and academic goals.

Besides, David (2016) stated that attending trainings is one of the avenues for the individual's self-improvement. It could help them sharpen their skills and get new ideas to be more effective and efficient; explore new ways of working through hands-on information that is specific in a certain field; break out of individual's comfort zone; get greater focus by relearning classic techniques; and absorb the energy of like-minded individuals.

Lastly, Felipe (2015) mentioned that it is the goal of the Department of Education that every teachers will become not only efficient but also effective. It is in this mission that today, a lot of trainings and seminars are being conducted to improve and develop the craft of each mentor in school. These trainings and seminars will help create an effective learning environment, improve coaching-learning situations, become keep updated on modern instructional devices and inspire others to become better coaches in the modern standards. Since the Department of Education is offering free trainings and seminars, teachers and coaches must grab this opportunity for self-improvement.

Implications

Being a national winner in campus journalism is truly a great accomplishment. However, the inquiry of the researchers uncovered that these highly successful coaches also have challenging stories and experiences behind their success; adversities surround most of the corners of the coaches' lives. This calls for teachers, administrators, the Department of Education, and other stakeholders for immediate action and improvement on the implementation of campus journalism in the Philippines.

This study implied that school paper advisers could gain lessons and insights from the experiences of national winning coaches in campus journalism. This would help them strengthen their sense of responsibility, courage, passion, truthfulness, and other desirable journalistic values in their writing. They must also be open-minded to the criticisms and suggestions given by other winning coaches. Aside from that, they must also engage themselves in training on campus journalism for them to get more knowledge and skills in coaching writers.

On the other hand, administrators can employ policies and objectives that can help solve the dilemma of coaches. They can also link with the higher-ups in the Department of Education to help them design and provide programs and actions to address the compelling situation of national winners in campus journalism. Furthermore, administrators should help winning coaches to grow in campus journalism and become productive citizens.

In addition, the result of the study also denoted that the Department of Education should strengthen the journalism program in schools by requiring them to conduct school-based journalism competitions before competing at a higher level of competition. Also, they must provide financial provisions to coaches who have won in the lower-level competition so that they may not be forced to use their resources to join the National Schools Press Conference. The region should also partner with actual media practitioners to help them choose, evaluate, and improve the journalistic skills of these budding coaches. This way, they can increase their chances of winning at the highest level of competition.

Recommendations for Further Research

This study explores the experiences of national winning coaches in the field of campus journalism. However, this qualitative investigation is limited only to the experiences of five (5) selected coaches and their fellow journalism coaches in the different schools of the Division of Davao del Norte. The implications suggest that further research should be conducted through quantitative method or mixed method applying larger sample of the participants to validate all the claims and responses of the participants in this study.

Moreover, because this study focuses on the Division of Davao del Norte only, further research be done on other Divisions wherein numerous national winning coaches are in campus journalism. Furthermore, further research can also be addressed to provide solutions to the difficulties experienced by national winning coaches in campus journalism. It may include the matters of coaching pedagogy and possible DepEd support. In this way, national winning coaches in campus journalism will be helped as they try to overcome the barriers

that hinder them from attaining self-actualization and validation for the victory they have accomplished.

Lastly, since the findings of this study were viewed from the lens of the national winning coaches in campus journalism, research may be conducted to determine the untold stories of student journalists, which have a direct relationship with national winning coaches in campus journalism.

References

- Aguilar, E. (2021). How coaching can impact teachers, principals, and students. George Lucas Educational Foundation.
- Aleccia, D. (2018). Why good educators are lifelong learners. Eastern Washington University.
- Anney, V. N. (2014). Ensuring the quality of the findings of qualitative research: Looking at trustworthiness criteria. Semantic Scholar.
- Assaroudi, A., Heshmati, F., Armat, M. & Ebadi, A., Vaismoradi, M. (2018). Directed qualitative content analysis: the description and elaboration of its underpinning methods and data analysis process. DOI: 10.1177/1744987117741667
- Attakorn, K. et al. (2015). Soft skills of coaches in the secondary schools of Khon Kaen Secondary Educational Service Area 25. *Procedia—Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 112, 1010–1013.
- Austin, Z. (2015). Qualitative research: Data collection, analysis, and management. *The Canadian Journal of Hospital Management*. [https://doi: 10.4212/cjhp.v68i3.1456](https://doi.org/10.4212/cjhp.v68i3.1456).
- Baxter, J. and Eyles, J. (1997) Evaluating qualitative research in social geography: Establishing “Rigor” in interview analysis. *Transactions of the Institute of British Geographers*, 22, 505-525. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1111/j.0020-2754.1997.00505.x>.
- Bird, F. (2018). Why is it important to keep yourself updated with currents affairs and news? The Consortium 2018.
- Bloom, B., and Crabtree, B. F. (2006). The qualitative research interview. *Medical Education*, 40(4), 314–321. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2929.2006.02418.x>
- Bouchillon, E. (2021). How to keep up with trends in journalism? *Stud Educ Eval*. 1997;23:257–73
- Bowen, G. (2018). Document analysis as a qualitative research method. *Qualitative Research Journal* 9(2):27-40. <https://doi.org/10.3316/QRJ0902027>.
- Brent, A. (2020). What is journalism? American Press Institute 2020.
- Brock, D. (2018). The importance of setbacks. Business 2 Community Partners In Excellence.
- Broward, F. (2017). High school journalism resource study (Doctoral dissertation). Retrieved from Digital Repository at the University of Maryland. <https://doi:10.13016/M2N589>.
- Brown, A. (2017). The importance of seminars and trainings in improving coaches performance. Teacher Essay.
- Caan, L. (2016). Exploring alternative ways of assessing prior knowledge, its components and their relation to student achievement: A mathematics-based case study. *Stud Educ Eval*. 2007;33:320–37.
- Cabedoche, B. (2019). New challenges for journalism education A contribution to Unesco Politics. Leif Kampf, Nico Carpentier, Andreas Hepp and all. *Journalism, Representation and the Public Sphere* editions Lumiere, pp. 57-68, 2015. ffhah- 02025490.
- Chiaburu, D. (2016). Exposure to bullying behaviours and support from co-workers and supervisors: A three-way interaction and the effect on health and well-being. *International Archives of Occupational and Environmental Health*
- Chu, D. (2015). Teacher/coach orientation and role socialization: A description and explanation. *Journal of Teaching in Physical Education*, 3(2), 3-8.
- Cresswell, J. W. (2007). Five qualitative approaches to inquiry. *Qualitative inquiry and research design: Choosing among five approaches*. Thousands Oaks: Sage Publications.
- Creswell, J. W. (2013). *Qualitative inquiry & research design: Choosing among five approaches* (3rd ed.).
- Coady, M. (2021). Money causes stress... do you know why? *The Journal of Special Education* 18(1984):101-107.
- Cortes, J. (2014). Campus Journalism: What Now and What Next. Retrieved: January 25, 2018, from <https://www.campusjournal.com/>.
- Curtis, K. (2016). How to bounce back from a tough loss. Coach Up Nation.
- Curtis, M. (2019). The importance of molding your coaching around your journalists. Airborne Athletics, Inc. 1701 W 94th St.
- David, E. (2018). *Life in classrooms*. New York, NY: Teachers College Press.
- David, P. (2016). The importance of training and development in the workplace. Business Insight Ltd.
- Drew, C. (2020). 5 Key principles of ‘thick description’ in research (2020). *The Qualitative Report*, 11(3), 538-549.
- Dyson, O. (2017). Our Universities: Institutional Pride. *The Journal of Special Education* 18(1984):101-107.
- Eccles J. and Wigfields M. (1994). *Expectancy-Value Theory*. Chicago Illinois: CME Group Foundation.
- Estella, P. (2020). Educating the educators: An evaluation of the preparedness of elementary school teachers in Los Baños, Laguna,

Philippines for journalism instruction and internet-mediated learning 1.

- Felipe, R. (2015). The importance of seminars and trainings in improving coaches performance. *Teacher Essay*.
- Flemming, J. (2020). Ensuring honesty in qualitative research. *International Research Association*.
- Flynn, S. and Korcuska, J. (2018). Credible phenomenological research: A Mixed-Methods Study. *Counselor Education and Supervision*. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ceas.12092>.
- Fossheim, H. and Ingierd, H. (2015). Internet research ethics. Available at: <https://press.nordicopenaccess.no/index.php/noasp/catalog/view/3/1/9-1>.
- Garcia, M. (2021). The importance of training employees: 11 benefits. *Career Guide*.
- Gavin, M. (2020). Optimism and physical health: A meta-analytic review. *Annals of Behavioral Medicine*, 37, 239–256. doi: 10.1007/s12160-009-9111-x.
- Graham, S., Andrew, C., & Maxwell, S. (2016). Teaching secondary students to write effectively. Washington, DC: National Center for Education Evaluation and Regional Assistance (NCEE 2017-4002), Institute of Education Sciences, U.S. Department of Education.
- Gracey, C., Azzara, C. & Reinherz, H. (2016). Screening for school entry. Screening revisited: A Survey of U. S. requirements." *The Journal of Special Education* 18(1984):101-107.
- Guba, E. G. (1999). Paradigmatic controversies, contradictions, and emerging confluences. In N. K. Denzin & Y. S. Lincoln (Eds.), *The Handbook of Qualitative Research* (2nd ed., pp. 163–188).
- Guest, G., Macqueen, K., & Namey, E. (2016). *Applied Thematic Analysis*. Sage Publication.
- Haas, M. (2016). *15 Fulfilling Ways to be Diligent*. The Thought & Expression Company.
- Hailikari, T., Nevgi A., & Lindblom-Ylänne S. (2018). Exploring alternative ways of assessing prior knowledge, its components and their relation to student achievement: A mathematics-based case study. *Stud Educ Eval*. 2007;33:320–37.
- Harrison, P. (2017). Exposure to bullying behaviours and support from co-workers and supervisors: A three-way interaction and the effect on health and well-being. *International Archives of Occupational and Environmental Health*.
- Harvey, L. (2019). Transferability. *Social Research Glossary, Quality Research International*. <http://www.qualityresearchinternational.com/socialresearch/>.
- Hassan, T. (2021). Importance of continuous learning and up skilling. *People Matters Pte. Ltd*.
- Hobson, A. J. (2016), “Judgementoring and how to avert it: Introducing ONSIDEMentoring forbeginning teachers”, *International Journal of Mentoring and Coaching in Education*, Vol. 5 No. 2,pp. 87-110.
- Holms, M. (2016). Trust is one of the most important aspects of relationships in work place. *The Classroom*. Leaf Group Education.
- Hsieh, H., & Shannon, S. (2005). Three approaches to qualitative content analysis. *Qualitative Health Research*. DOI: 10.1177/1049732305276687.
- Hunt, V. (2016). The pros and cons of having high expectations for everyone around you. *The Thought & Expression Company*.
- Jaffe, R. (2017). Trust is one of the most important aspects of relationships in a work place. *The Classroom*. Leaf Group Education.
- James, O. (2018). Exploring alternative ways of assessing prior knowledge, its components and their relation to student achievement: A mathematics-based case study. *Stud Educ Eval*. 2007;33:320–37.
- Javed, M., and Iqbal, M. (2015), Mentoring: A mechanism for improving teacher's performance in Khyber-Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan. *International Journal of Economics, Commerce and Management*, 3(9), 410-428.
- Kashyap, S. (2020). Importance of team collaboration at workplace. *Proofhub Organization*.
- Kernagan, B. (2016). Our Universities: Institutional Pride. *The Journal of Special Education* 18(1984):101-107.
- Korn, S. (2014). Student Journalism and Student Voice. Retrieved: November 10, 2017, from <https://www.thecrimson.com/>.
- Laguador, J. (2013). Developing students’ attitude leading towards a life-changing career. *Lyceum of the Philippines University Journal*, Vol. 43 No. 1, pp. 168-191
- Lawrence, E. (2016). Challenges to monetary policy in an educational context. *Central Banking Studies at the Central Bank of Sri Lanka*, Colombo.
- Lazar, J., Feng, J., & Meiselwitz, G. (2007). Understanding Web Credibility: A Synthesis of the Research Literature. *Foundations and Trends® in Human-Computer*.
- Lent, P. (2018). The importance of work experience. *Careers Writers Association, Wendy Reed March*.
- Llama, R. (2017). The importance of training: Training and development Process. *Coach Up Nation*.
- Lincoln, Y. S., & Guba, E. G. (1985). *Naturalistic inquiry*. Newbury Park, CA: Sage Publications.
- Mackenzie, D. (2018). High school journalism resource study (Doctoral dissertation). Retrieved from Digital Repository at the

University of Maryland. <https://doi:10.13016/M2N589>.

Maddock, I. (2016). Exploring alternative ways of assessing prior knowledge, its components and their relation to student achievement: A mathematics-based case study. *Stud Educ Eval*, 2007;33:320–37.

Maksl, A. (2020). More than yearbooks or newspapers: High school journalism is about the process. Retrieved: January 25, 2018, from <https://www.campusjournal.com/>.

Martic, K. (2017). Trust is one of the most important aspects of relationships in work place. The Classroom. Leaf Group Education.

Martinez, J. (2021). Academic coaching, student engagement, and instructor best practices. Walden Dissertations and Doctoral Studies.

Marroquin, B. (2018). The negative attitudes of teachers' impact on students. The Classroom. Leaf Group Education.

Mason, M. (2017). Transforming early childhood education through critical reflection. Contemporary issues in early childhood. Sage Publication.

Mazer, W. (2018). Our Universities: Institutional Pride. Department of Communication and Journalism Chittagong University Chittagong-4331.

McIntyre, R. (2016). Why your commitments are important! The Thought & Expression Company.

Miles, M. B. (2013). *Qualitative data analysis: A sourcebook of new methods* (2nd ed.). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.

Misasi, K. (2016). Effective coaching: Improving teacher practice and outcomes for all learners. Transforming State Systems to Improve Outcomes for Students. WestEd NCSI.

Mohammed, Z. (2020). The advantages & disadvantages of practice & drills in teaching. Hearts Newspaper.

Montefiore, S. (2021). The importance of continuously learning from others. Exploring the breadth of human experience (p. 41–60). Plenum Press.

Moore, E., and Llompart, J. (2017). Collecting, transcribing, analysing and presenting plurilingual interactional data. *Research-publishing.net*. <https://doi.org/10.14705/rpnet.2017.emmd2016.638>.

Morgan, K. (2020). What are the benefits of attending seminars? A description and explanation. *Journal of Teaching in Physical Education*, 3(2), 3-8.

Morgan, S., Macdonald, L., Pullon, S., & McKinlay, E. (2016). Case study observational research: A framework for conducting case study research where observation data are the focus. Research Gate GmbH.

Moses, R. & Mohamad, M. (2019). Challenges faced by students and teachers on writing skills in esl contexts: A Literature Review. Faculty of Education, Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia.

Naz, K. (2019). Effects of teachers' professional competence on students' academic achievements at secondary school level in Muzaffarabad District. GRIN Verlag,

Nortajuddin, A. (2020). Challenges of teaching journalism in rural areas. *The ASEAN Post*. Digital Media Nusantara.

Nolan, S. (2017). The importance of molding your coaching around your journalists. Airborne Athletics, Inc. 1701 W 94th St.

Omay, F. (2020). The campus journalists of PLSNHS. DepEd City of Naga, Cebu

Page, M. (2019). Why it's good to ask for help? InnerDrive Ltd, 2006 – 2019.

Parsloe, E. & Wray, M. (2013). Coaching and Mentoring. Retrieved: September 18, 2018.

Patterson, B. (2020). Performance reviews: a smart guide to self-evaluating. Airborne Athletics, Inc. 1701 W 94th St.

Patton, M. Q. (2002). *Qualitative research and evaluation methods*, (3rd ed.). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.

Peterson, C. (2020). The future of optimism. *American Psychologist*, 55, 44–55. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1037/0003-066X.55.1.44>

Podany, A. (2017). Ethical considerations in pediatric research. In: Buck ML, Manasco KB, eds. *PedSAP 2017 Book 1 Research and Study Design in Pediatrics*. Lenexa, KS: American College of Clinical Pharmacy; 2015.

Polit, D.F. and Beck, C.T. (2014). *Essentials of nursing research: Appraising evidence for nursing practice*. 8th Edition, Lippincott Williams & Wilkins, Philadelphia.

Polkinghorne, D. E. (2005). Language and meaning: Data collection in qualitative research. *Journal of Counseling Psychology*, 52(2), 137–145. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-0167.52.2.137>

Powers, T. (1973). *Behavior: The control of perception*. 1st ed. Aldine de Gruyter

Puligsi, V. (2016). The importance of molding your coaching around your journalists. Airborne Athletics, Inc. 1701 W 94th St.

Renk, P. (2016). The disappointments every writer must face. Department of Communication and Journalism Chittagong University Chittagong-4331.

Rhodes, C.P. and Houghton-Hill, S. (2000). The linkage of continuing professional development and the classroom experience of pupils: Barriers perceived by senior managers of some secondary schools. *Journal of In-Service Education/General*, 26, 423-435. <https://doi:10.1080/13674580200200184>.

- Ribiero, S. (2020). The real benefits of team collaboration in the workplace. *Social and Behavioral Sciences* 93. ResearchGate GmbH.
- Robins, D. (2018). Why is it so important to learn from experts? LinkedIn.
- Robinson, C. (2016). Challenges to monetary policy in an educational context. *Central Banking Studies at the Central Bank of Sri Lanka*, Colombo.
- Roomer, J. (2019). Why you need a strong commitment to your goals if you want to succeed. *American City Business Journals BizSpotlight*.
- Salazar, R. (2018). Insight from running a school newspaper. *National Board for Professional Teaching Standard*.
- Sarkhedi, B. (2020). Importance of having a positive attitude in life. Bennett, Coleman & Co. Ltd.
- Seligman, M. (2018). Learned optimism: How to change your mind and your life. *Journal of Applied Social Psychology*
- Schleicher, A. (2015). Building a high-quality teaching profession: Lessons from around the World. OECD Publishing, Paris, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1787/9789264113046-en>.
- Scott, A. (2018). Ethical considerations in pediatric research. In: Buck ML, Manasco KB, eds. *PedSAP 2017 Book 1 Research and Study Design in Pediatrics*. Lenexa, KS: American College of Clinical Pharmacy; 2015.
- Shanks, R. (2017). "Mentoring beginning teachers: professional learning for mentees and mentors". *International Journal of Mentoring and Coaching in Education*, Vol. 6 No. 3, pp. 158-163.
- Shenton, A. K. (2004). Strategies for ensuring trustworthiness in qualitative research projects. *Education for Information*, 22, 63-75.
- Sicinski, A. (2021). When all is lost... How to bounce back from defeat stronger than before. *Psychology Today*.
- Skinner, B. F. (1990). A brief survey of operant behavior. Retrieved January 26, 2012, from The B.F. Skinner Foundation Website: <http://www.bfskinner.org/BFSkinner/SurveyOperantBehavior.html>
- Smith, M. (2017). The importance of stakeholders in project management success. Opportunity Education Foundation, Inc.
- Smith, J. (2019). Biz tip of the week: Failure can teach us important lessons in our lives. *The Arizona Daily Star*
- International Journal of Mentoring and Coaching in Education*, Vol. 6 No. 3, pp. 158-163.
- International Journal of Mentoring and Coaching in Education*, Vol. 6 No. 3, pp. 158-163.
- International Journal of Mentoring and Coaching in Education*, Vol. 6 No. 3, pp. 158-163.
- International Journal of Mentoring and Coaching in Education*, Vol. 6 No. 3, pp. 158-163
- Srivastava, P. (2018). Significance of commitment in life. *New Delhi Times*. A-2/59 Safdarjung Enclave New Delhi 110029
- Streubert, H. J. & Carpenter, D. R. (1995). *Qualitative research in nursing: Advancing the humanistic imperative*. Philadelphia: J. B. Lippincott Company.
- Streubert, H. J. & Carpenter, D. R. (1995). *Qualitative research in nursing: Advancing the humanistic imperative*. Philadelphia: J. B. Lippincott Company.
- Streubert, H. J. & Carpenter, D. R. (1995). *Qualitative research in nursing: Advancing the humanistic imperative*. Philadelphia: J. B. Lippincott Company.
- Stake, A. (2018). *Qualitative research in nursing (2nd ed.)*. Garsington Road, Oxford: Blackwell Science Limited
- Steven, G. (2021). Bouncing back after a tough loss. *Coaching Kidz*
- Sutton, J. (2015). Qualitative research: Data collection, analysis, and management. *The Canadian Journal of Hospital Management*. [https://doi: 10.4212/cjhp.v68i3.1456](https://doi:10.4212/cjhp.v68i3.1456).
- Sutton, J., and Austin, Z. (2015). Qualitative research: Data collection, analysis, and management. *The Canadian Journal of Hospital Management*. [https://doi: 10.4212/cjhp.v68i3.1456](https://doi:10.4212/cjhp.v68i3.1456).
- Tews, A. (2017). Exposure to bullying behaviours and support from co-workers and supervisors: A three-way interaction and the effect on health and well-being. *International Archives of Occupational and Environmental Health*
- Tichenor, A. (2020). Challenges of high school journalism advising; a study and guidebook to improve publications.
- Tobin, G. and Begley, C. (2004). Methodological rigor within a qualitative framework. *Journal of Advanced Nursing* 48(4):388-96. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2648.2004.03207.x>.
- Trochim, W.M.K., (2006). Qualitative validity. Available at <http://www.socialresearchmethods.net/kb/qualval>.
- Turner, D. (2016). Triangulation in qualitative research. *Nurse Researcher*, 20 (2), <https://journals.rcni.com/doi/pdfplus/10.7748/nr2012.11.20.2.40.c9442>
- Ullah, M. (2021). Scholarly turn of journalism education: redesigning curricula at University level in Bangladesh. Department of Communication and Journalism Chittagong University Chittagong-4331

- Van Nieuwerburgh, C. (2017). *An introduction to coaching skills: A practical guide.* London, UK: Sage.
- Varvel, C. (2015). Pedagogical roles and competencies of University teachers practicing in the E-learning environment. vol 14, no 3 (2013).
- Weinstein, J. (2016). *The problem of rural education in the Philippines.* London, UK: Sage.
- Wiley, M. (2014). *Case study research design and methods (5th ed.).* Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage. 282 pages. (ISBN 978-1-4522-4256-9).
- Yin, R. K. (2009). *Case study research: Design and methods (4th Ed.).* Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Daniel D. Somosot Jr., MAEd

Dagohoy National High School
Department of Education – Philippines

Carla Mae P. Landasan

Dagohoy National High School
Department of Education – Philippines

Rovejane S. Salvacion

Dagohoy National High School
Department of Education – Philippines